

A guide to using landscape genomics for the conservation and use of plant diversity

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Should you have any comments on the content and analysis explained in this manual please contact the corresponding authors: mvzonneveld@gmail.com, eomondi2008@gmail.com, info@worldveg.org.

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World Vegetable Center
PO Box 42
Shanhua, Tainan 74199
Taiwan
+886 6 583 7801
info@worldveg.org
worldveg.org

中華民國外交部
MINISTRY OF FOREIGN AFFAIRS
REPUBLIC OF CHINA (TAIWAN)

農業部
MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE

G2P-SOL

Linking genetic resources, genomes and phenotypes
of Solanaceous crops

A guide to using landscape genomics for the conservation and use of plant diversity

Emmanuel Omondi

World Vegetable Center, Shanhua, Taiwan

Ya-Ping Lin

World Vegetable Center, Shanhua, Taiwan

Maarten van Zonneveld

World Vegetable Center, Shanhua, Taiwan

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Summary

Climate change and environmental disturbances due to human activities are posing significant threats to biodiversity, which, in turn, affects food security and social stability. Many species are undergoing range shifts and fitness declines, while others have developed adaptive traits to avoid extinction. When genetically controlled, these traits undergo natural selection, leading to the development of locally adapted populations (LA), where specific alleles become prevalent due to their fitness advantage in specific environments. This has led to a growing research interest in landscape genomics (LSG), which combines landscape ecology and genomics to detect signatures of local adaptation.

LSG is particularly valuable for identifying the loci responsible for adaptive genetic variation across landscapes. The approach, though relatively new, has shown its feasibility in crop and animal species, revealing adaptive traits in species like wheat, maize, barley, sorghum, eggplant, goats, and chicken. Modeling genomic and environmental data has allowed researchers to predict crop fitness in future climates, benefiting conservation efforts and crop improvement programs. For example, studies have identified populations at risk of extinction, guiding ex-situ conservation and assisted gene flow strategies. Using LSG to predict species' genetic responses to climate gradients is helping shape conservation strategies to maintain biodiversity.

While LSG holds promise, there are significant challenges, particularly the issue of false positives when identifying loci linked to local adaptation. False positives may arise when genetic drift or demographic effects mimic local adaptation patterns. Fortunately, continuous improvement of methods in environmental association analyses is helping to control for false positives. Moreover, distinguishing between correlated environmental factors remains challenging in LSG studies, as some correlations may be due to covarying factors not included in the analysis. Despite these challenges, LSG's potential to mine adaptive genes for crop improvement and to inform conservation strategies is vast.

This comprehensive manual provides valuable insights into the fundamental steps and critical considerations needed for undertaking successful LSG studies. Within its pages, we have carefully selected a few commonly applied methods. However, it is important to note that various techniques are available to researchers depending on their computational capacity and proficiency. We also assume that the user has basic R program skills to be able to apply the scripts provided in the manual. Furthermore, we present a collection of R scripts that have been curated to achieve specific outcomes and create simplified graphical displays of the results for easier interpretation. We acknowledge that study scenarios can vary widely, and the complexity of each study can differ significantly depending on the organism being studied and the diverse landscapes involved. Links to additional detailed resources have also been provided to broaden the users' perspective.

SECTION A. OVERVIEW

1. Introduction

Landscape genomics is a growing research field that combines landscape factors and genomics to detect signatures of local adaptation of plant populations (Rellstab et al., 2015a). It holds a great promise to detect genomic variation associated to environmental adaptation of crops and their wild relatives (Campbell et al., 2025). Populations of plant species, wild relatives and landraces of crops, are ongoing interactions with the environment, which can drive selection for traits to adapt to local environmental conditions. This can take decades, centuries, or longer. When these traits are under genetic control, natural selection leads to the development of locally adapted populations. Local adaptation (LA) is when local populations show higher fitness than foreign ones. During the selection, the best-fitting alleles for the local environment become prevalent through positive selection. These alleles are being conserved in alleles and wild relatives in the wild, on the farm, or in genebanks, and provide a genetic resource to develop new varieties adapted to changing climates and changing palates. However, a lot of this adaptive genetic variation has not yet been identified because of the costs of phenotyping large amounts of landraces and conserving crops of wild relatives. LSG provides a promising tool to screen larger collections of plant genetic resources to target landraces and crop wild relatives with putative SNPS associated with environmental factors for further screening.

1.1. Existing applications

The landscape genomics approach – also known as the ‘environmental genome-wide association study’ (envGWAS), was applied initially in ecological and evolutionary studies (Hoban et al., 2016). However, landscape genomics is now emerging as important tool in the conservation and use of genetic resources that can complement other tools, such as genome-phenotype association studies and on-farm evaluation, applied to crop improvement and conservation programs (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A scheme showing how landscape genomics can complement other tools in crop improvement, and its role in trait discovery from genebanks, to variety development (modified from Rellstab et al., 2015).

The literature demonstrates its feasibility in assessing patterns in crop adaptation and plant genetic resources studies to detect candidate loci associated with environmental factors. This shows that it can be applied with landraces and crop wild relatives, and both self-pollinating and outcrossing crops. Most examples of application of landscape genomics for conserving and using plant genetic resources are from studies with landraces of self-pollinating cereals. For instance, Hanif et al. (2021) characterized wheat populations from Pakistan and Iran, identifying several loci using agroclimatic data in a genome-wide association. Their selective sweep analysis identified chromosome hits colocalized with loci associated with local adaptability and some genes related to flowering time and grain size. Landscape genomics was applied in barley to identify the climatic factors and candidate loci driving local adaptation in the Qinghai-Tibetan plateau using 157 diverse naked barley landrace accessions (Chen et al., 2023). The study successfully established that the genomic diversity of the landraces could be traced back to the geographical and environmental diversity of the landscape. Moreover, 136 markers were associated with precipitation, temperature, and radiation. The study also mapped 477 genes, close to eight of the markers identified, some of which are involved in cold stress and regulation of flowering time.

Still on self-pollinating crops, for barley, a recent study by Chang et al. (2022) also applied landscape genomics to investigate the association of genomic variation with the geographic and environmental factors in wild barley populations of the southern Levant. This study aimed to determine the extent of genetic variation that reflects local adaptation in the barley wild relatives to identify functional genetic diversity for barley improvement. Even though their genome scan identified adaptation signatures, they disappeared after correction for population structure, showing the importance of adjusting Environmental GWAS for population structure. Finally, for sorghum, Lasky et al. (2015), using 1943 georeferenced sorghum landraces, tested the hypothesis that if associations between single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) alleles and environment of origin in crop landraces reflect adaptation, then these could be used to predict phenotypic variation for adaptive traits. After using SNP-environment and SNP-phenotype associations to identify loci underlying adaptive trait variation, they identified several SNPs near genes of interest strongly associated with the environment, although not among those strongly associated with the phenotype. This is a clear example of leveraging the genome-environment association to the genome-phenotype association in selecting climate resilience traits and germplasm identification strategies;

In maize, an outcrossing cereal, Westengen et al. (2012) identified 79 SNPs associated with maximum temperature during the growing season in a panel of 48 accessions of African maize. The accessions were selected based on their representation of their historical and recent germplasm introduction in Africa. This way, a high selection pressure from varying climatic stresses would be catered for. The SNP associated with the environmental variables were located in abiotic stress tolerance genes, making interesting candidates for local adaptation. Li et al. (2019) also assessed 1,143 diverse maize accessions for environmental adaptation. The collection including landraces collected from 20 countries and elite breeding lines of tropical lowland, highland, subtropical/midaltitude and temperate ecological zones. Based on 355,442 high-quality single nucleotide polymorphisms, 13 genomic regions were detected as being under selection of which two regions associated significantly with environmental parameters via Environmental GWAS (EnvGWAS) and 146 genes were enriched. The regions identified in the study are promising candidates for further exploration in maize breeding. Here, the potential of a landscape genomics approach to help breeders better understand the implications of the genomic footprint on crop environmental adaptation and explore more targeted accessions with high breeding relevance is highlighted.

Regarding crop wild relatives, landscape genomics has been applied to identify the environmental drivers of the genetic diversity among African wild eggplant and landraces (Omondi et al., 2024). These species have shown moderate levels of interspecific hybridization in crossing experiments (Bukonya Carasco, 1995; Plazas et al., 2016) and between domesticated eggplants and their wild ancestors (Meyer et al., 2012). This study identified three hundred and ninety-three candidate adaptive signatures that could separate the populations in a pattern similar to the environmental separation. This finding suggested that the genome-environment

association effectively identified markers that are highly linked to the selection at the natural sight. Some of the signatures of selection are also located in genes that confer resilience to biotic and abiotic stresses such as cold and drought. Combined with analysis of the adaptive landscape, the study provides valuable insights into the environmental adaptation of eggplant CWR with clear applications for breeders in selecting germplasm that is potentially adapted to different environmental stress and use of the selected putative adaptive signals in marker-assisted selection after verification in gene expression studies.

Still on crop wild relatives, Massa et al. (2024) implemented a landscape genomics approach to understanding the adaptive genetic variability of *A. duranensis* represented in an *ex-situ* peanut germplasm collection using a panel of 2,810 SNP markers. By incorporation of bioclimatic variables for genotype-environment associations and using the latent factor mixed model (LFMM2) method, they found genomic signatures of environmental adaptation. The allele frequencies for the candidate adaptive SNP loci were significantly correlated predominantly with temperature-related bioclimatic variables. Further field evaluations on leaf spot disease resistance revealed that the genomic regions involved in adaptation were co-localized with genomic regions potentially involved in leaf spot resistance. These outcomes show the potential use of wild *A. duranensis* to enable the simultaneous introgression of favorable alleles into cultivated peanuts. The study also highlights the importance of the application of landscape genomics in *ex situ* collections of peanut and other crop wild relatives to effectively identify favorable alleles and germplasm for incorporation into breeding programs.

1.2. Manual overview

This manual's primary goal is to provide comprehensive step-by-step guidance on landscape genomics (LSG) analysis, interpretations, and applications of the results (Figure 2: Steps 1–4). It aims to equip researchers, practitioners and students with tools, methodologies and theoretical frameworks to conduct LSG studies.

Section A –this section, introduces the topic.

Section B explains how to do landscape genomics with R statistics at the hand of a use a case study with eggplant landraces (Omondi et al., 2025). This means that the analysis shown in this book have gone through a peer review process and therefore scientifically solid and verifiable. The case study is at the heart of this manual. It consists of four parts.

- Chapter 2. Import of environmental and location data, provides a brief methodology and guideline for linking environmental data to species locations using geospatial functions in R statistics.
- Chapter 3. Import and population structure of genomic data, provides methodology and guidelines for collecting genomic data (sequencing) and conducting basic population genomics with R statistics.
- Chapter 4. Landscape genomics to identify adaptive alleles, offers guidelines for designing strategies that capture genetic and environmental variation across landscapes. Explain step-by-step procedures for performing key analyses, such as identifying loci under selection and mapping adaptive genetic variation.
- Chapter 5. Modelling genomic dynamics at landscape level and under climate change, explains a brief methodology to model the genetic-environment relationship at landscape level and to measure genomic offset and shifts in genomic optimums of using future climate predictions.

Section C – this discusses the variety of genomic tools, the limitations and future directions of landscape genomics, and provide concluding remarks. This section will give an overview of additional resources and tools that can complement what this manual has covered. Information will be provided about recommended software tools, databases, and online resources for landscape genomic research. Educational resources, workshops, and courses for those interested in gaining in-depth knowledge and skills in LSG. This section will then briefly discuss some challenges (i.e., addressing common challenges and limitations in landscape genomic studies, such as issues with data quality, resolution, and computational demands) and future directions. By covering these aspects, we believe this manual will be a valuable resource for guiding research design, implementation, analysis, and application in LSG. It will ultimately contribute to a better understanding of how genetic diversity and environmental factors interact across landscapes.

Figure 2: Main steps in landscape genomics.

NOTE: This manual covers step 1-4 of the figure and they are described in Chapters 2-5 in Section B of this manual. Chapter 2, 3, and 4 I cover steps 1 and 2. These steps involve preparing the genomic and environmental data and identifying the genomic basis of local adaptation through GEA and F_{ST} approaches. Steps 3 and 4 are covered in Chapter 5, describing the prediction of (mal) adaptability across the landscape. Step 5 is not included in this manual but it briefly explains the validations. Figure adapted from Capblancq et al. (2020).

1.3. Data availability

Data used in this manual is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.08kpr5c7>. It has been used in Omondi et al. (2025), available at <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.17229>. The data includes 331 accessions of domesticated eggplants from South Asia, conserved at World Vegetable Center genebanks, which has been used as part of the “Linking genetic resources, genomes and phenotypes of Solanaceous crops (G2P-SOL)” collaborative research project. The accessions were georeferenced based on the passport data. We highly recommend reading this paper to get further insights on the potential, methodologies, and caveats with agriculture landscape genomics. If having difficulties in downloading data or in analysis explained in this manual, contact the corresponding authors: mvzonneveld@gmail.com, eomondi2008@gmail.com, , info@worldveg.org.

SECTION B. CASE STUDY ON EGGPLANT LANDSCAPE GENOMICS

2. Import of location and environmental data

Aims

- Import species location data and corresponding environmental data
- Extracting values from environmental variables for each species location data
- Selecting uncorrelated environmental variables for landscape genomics analysis

2.1. Starting in the R environment

All analysis in this manual will be done with R statistics (R Core Team, 2024) and R Studio (Posit team, 2024). For those who are not familiar with these two software tools: R is a free software environment for statistical computing and graphics. R Studio is a software application that makes R easier to use. First, make sure that R statistics and R Studio are downloaded. This manual was built in R version 4.4.0, which is the recommended version to use for the analysis explained. There are several online sources that explain the function and installation of these two software applications. Here are a few.

- <https://www.r-project.org/>
- <https://rstudio-education.github.io/hopr/starting.html>

For incipient users of R, there are many online tools to learn the basics of R and the basics of using R Studio:

- <https://cran.r-project.org/manuals.html>
- <https://education.rstudio.com/learn/beginner/>

For this manual, we expect a basic experience of using R. While all functions and steps are explained in detail so that any user can apply the analysis themselves, more R proficiency will help users to better understand and interpret the R Script examples presented.

To start, we must set up our R environment. Open RStudio and create a new project via: • File > New Project • Select 'New Directory' • For Project Type, select 'New Project' • For the Directory name, call it something like "Landscape genomics" (without the quotes) • For the subdirectory, select somewhere you will remember (like My Documents or Desktop). The directory would be the default location where R will look for files that you want to load and where it will put the files you save.

2.1.1. Libraries

Here, we provide the libraries and functions that are used in this manual. However, we shall still be loading the package libraries at the required step to make it easy to recall the functions. Check to see that you have correctly installed the libraries. Some libraries might require direct installation from GitHub sources and some may require installation through BiocManager that require first an installation of Bioconductor package. Some of the functions in the packages provided may be found in alternatives R packages that you may prefer. Some libraries may be retired by the time you use this manual, so check carefully the packages to which the retired functions might have been transferred.

```
# Libraries required
```

```
#devtools (Wickham et al., 2022)
```

```
#allows you to easily install and manage other packages from various repositories, including CRAN, GitHub, Bioconductor, and more.
```

```
if(!require('devtools')) {
```

```

install.packages('devtools')
}; library(devtools)

#BiocManager (Morgan and Ramos, 2024)
#allows the installation and management of packages from the Bioconductor project.
if (!require("BiocManager", quietly = TRUE)) {
  install.packages("BiocManager") #ensure that the appropriate Bioconductor installation is used with respect to the
  version of R in use regardless of the R and Bioconductor release cycles. }

#dplyr (Wickham et al., 2023)
#used for data manipulation
if (!require('dplyr')) {
  install.packages('dplyr')
}; library(dplyr)

#rnatuarearth (Massicotte and South 2023)
#provides map data that can be visualized in other R packages
if (!require('rnatuarearth')) {
  install.packages('rnatuarearth')
}; library(rnatuarearth)

#ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016)
#for creating data visualization
if (!require('ggplot2')) {
  install.packages('ggplot2')
}; library(ggplot2)

#data.table (Barrett et al., 2023)
#Importing data in table format
if (!require('data.table')) {
  install.packages('data.table')
}; library(data.table)

#geodata (Hijmans et al., 2024)
#contains functions that facilitate access to geographic data for spatial analysis and mapping
if (!require('geodata')) {
  install.packages('geodata')
}; library(geodata)

#sf (Pebesna and Bivand. 2021)
#reads from and writes to spatial databases
if (!require('sf')) {
  install.packages('sf')
}; library(sf)

#raster (Hijmans, 2023)
#for creating, reading, manipulating, and writing raster data.
if (!require('raster')) {
  install.packages('raster')
}; library(raster)

#fuzzySim (Barbosa, 2015)
#Functions to compute as pair-wise fuzzy similarity
if (!require('fuzzySim')) {
  install.packages('fuzzySim')
}; library(fuzzySim)

```

```

#corrplot (Wei and Simko, 2024)
#Plotting results from correlation analysis
if (!require('corrplot')) {
  install.packages('corrplot')
}; library(corrplot)

#factoextra (Kassambara and Mundt (2020)
#to extract and visualize the output of exploratory multivariate data analyses, e.g., PCA
if(!require('factoextra')) {
  install.packages('factoextra')
}; library(factoextra)

#LEA (Frichot and Francois, 2015)
#population genomics, landscape genomics, and ecological association tests
if (!require("LEA")){
  BiocManager::install("LEA")
};library(LEA)

#pophelper (Francis, 2017)
#to analyze and visualize population structure
if(!require('pophelper')) {
  devtools::install_github('royfrancis/pophelper')
}; library(pophelper)

#vcfR (Knaus and Grünwald (2017)
#to allow easy manipulation and visualization of variant call format (VCF) data
if(!require('vcfR')) {
  install.packages('vcfR')
}; library(vcfR)

#adegenet (Jombart, 2008)
#for the Multivariate Analysis of Genetic Markers
if(!require('adegenet')) {
  install.packages('adegenet')
}; library(adegenet)

#sp (Pebesna and Bivand. 2013)
#provides S4 classes for importing, manipulating, and exporting spatial data in R
if(!require('sp')) {
  install.packages('sp')
}; library(sp)

#dartR (Gruber et al., 2018)
#Importing and Analysing 'SNP' and 'Silicodart' Data Generated by Genome-Wide Restriction Fragment Analysis
if(!require('dartR')) {
  install.packages('dartR')
}; library(dartR)

#tidyr (Wickham et al., 2024)
#to simplify the process of creating tidy data
if(!require('tidyr')) {
  install.packages('tidyr')
}; library(tidyr)

#RColorBrewer (Neuwirth 2022)
#For managing colors in r. Offere several color palletes

```

```

if(!require('RColorBrewer')) {
  install.packages('RColorBrewer')
}; library(RColorBrewer)

## Loading required package: RColorBrewer

#conStruct (Bradburd, 2024)
#uses genetic information to infer discrete population structure and assign ancestry of a set of genotyped samples
if(!require('conStruct')) {
  install.packages('conStruct')
}; library(conStruct)

#maps (Becker, 2023)
#for drawing geographical maps
if(!require('maps')) {
  install.packages('maps')
}; library(maps)

#scales (Wikham et. al., 2023)
#internal scaling infrastructure is used by ggplot2 and gives you tools to override the default breaks, labels, transformations, and palettes.
if(!require('scales')) {
  install.packages('scales')
}; library(scales)

#vegan (Oksanen et al., 2022)
#provides ordination methods, diversity analysis, and other functions for community and vegetation ecologists
if(!require('vegan')) {
  install.packages('vegan')
}; library(vegan)

#robust (Wang et al., 2024)
#Methods for robust statistics, notably for robust regression and robust multivariate analysis
if(!require('robust')) {
  install.packages('robust')
}; library(robust)

#qvalue (Storey et al., 2023)
#performs false discovery rate (FDR) estimation from a collection of p-values or test statistics with corresponding empirical null statistics.
if(!require('qvalue')) {
  install.packages('qvalue')
}; library(qvalue)

#lfmm (Jumentier, 2021)
#is to identify genetic polymorphisms that exhibit a high correlation with some environmental gradient or with the variables used as proxies for ecological pressures.
if(!require('lfmm')) {
  install.packages('lfmm')
}; library(lfmm)

#pcadapt (Privé, Florian, et al., 2020)
#performs genome scans to detect genes under selection based on population genomic data
if(!require('pcadapt')) {
  install.packages('pcadapt')
}; library(pcadapt)

```

```

#VennDiagram (Chen, 2022)
#contains a set of functions to generate high-resolution Venn and Euler plots
if(!require('VennDiagram')) {
  install.packages('VennDiagram')
}; library(VennDiagram)

```

2.1.2. Functions

The following functions are not part of the packages installed in section 2.1.1 above but have been developed for easy demonstration and interpretation of the results at various point in the manual. The use of the functions and the input elements are required before applying the functions are described in the scripts.

```

# hist_env()
# hist_env provides the distribution frequencies (histograms) of a set of variables
# of interest to allow a visual check for potential data transformation.
# 1. X: a data.frame object with rows corresponding to individuals and columns to
#     environmental variables
# Returns the histograms of the variables provided.
hist_env <- function(X = NULL) {
  X <- as.data.frame(X)
  for (i in 1:ncol(X)) {
    if (i == 2) {
      op <- par(ask=TRUE)
    }
    hist(X[, i], main="", xlab=colnames(X)[i])
    title(colnames(X)[i])
  }
  par(op)
}
# env_pruning()
# env_pruning applies a given VIF threshold to an environmental data set and
# removes collinear variables in an iterative way up to obtain a pruned data set
# with max(VIF) lower than the selected threshold.
# 1. X: an environmental data set with individuals by row and the variables by
#     column
# 2. vif.thr: the selected VIF threshold
# Returns list with two slots:
# 1. the pruned environmental data set
# 2. the correlation matrix associated with the pruned data set
env_pruning <- function(X = NULL, vif.thr = NULL) {

  cat("\n"); cat("When using this function, please cite:"); cat("\n")
  cat("[1] https://besjournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/2041-210X.12372")
  cat("\n"); cat("\n")
  res <- list()

  env_vif <- multicol(vars = X)
  while (length(which(env_vif$VIF > vif.thr)) >= 1) {
    t <- rownames(env_vif)[1]
    t <- which(colnames(X) == t)
    X <- X[, -t]
    env_vif <- multicol(vars = X)
    print(env_vif); cat("\n")
  }
}

```

```

res[[1]] <- X
res[[2]] <- cor(X)
names(res) <- c(paste0("Pruned environmental data set (VIF<", vif.thr, ")"), "Correlation matrix")
return(res)
}
# rdadapt() function
rdadapt<-function(rda,K){
loadings<-rda$CCA$v[,1:as.numeric(K)]
resscale <- apply(loadings, 2, scale)
resmaha <- covRob(resscale, distance = TRUE, na.action= na.omit, estim="pairwiseGK")$dist
lambda <- median(resmaha)/qchisq(0.5,df=K)
reschi2test <- pchisq(resmaha/lambda,K,lower.tail=FALSE)
qval <- qvalue(reschi2test)
q.values_rdadapt<-qval$qvalues
return(data.frame(p.values=reschi2test, q.values=q.values_rdadapt))
}
#outliers()
#The function for outliers here (Credits to Forester et al., 2018),
#where x is the vector of loadings and z is the standard deviation cut-off
outliers <- function(x,z){
lims <- mean(x) + c(-1, 1) * z * sd(x) ## Find loadings +/- z SD from mean loading
x[x < lims[1] | x > lims[2]] # Locus names in these tails
}
# adaptive_index()
#Adaptive index calculation based on the 'adaptive_index()' function (Credits Capblancq and Forester 2021)
adaptive_index <- function(RDA, K, env_pres, range = NULL, method = "loadings", scale_env, center_env){
# Formatting environmental rasters for projection
var_env_proj_pres <- as.data.frame(rasterToPoints(env_pres[[row.names(RDA$CCA$biplot)]]))
# Standardization of the environmental variables
var_env_proj_RDA <- as.data.frame(scale(var_env_proj_pres[,c(1,2)], center_env[row.names(RDA$CCA$biplot)],
scale_env[row.names(RDA$CCA$biplot)]))
# Predicting pixels genetic component based on RDA axes
Proj_pres <- list()
if(method == "loadings"){
for(i in 1:K){
ras_pres <- rasterFromXYZ(data.frame(var_env_proj_pres[,c(1,2)], Z =
as.vector(apply(var_env_proj_RDA[,names(RDA$CCA$biplot[,i])], 1, function(x) sum(x * RDA$CCA$biplot[,i]))), crs =
crs(env_pres))
names(ras_pres) <- paste0("RDA_pres_", as.character(i))
Proj_pres[[i]] <- ras_pres
names(Proj_pres)[i] <- paste0("RDA", as.character(i))
}
}
# Prediction with RDA model and linear combinations
if(method == "predict"){
pred <- predict(RDA, var_env_proj_RDA[,names(RDA$CCA$biplot[,i])], type = "lc")
for(i in 1:K){
ras_pres <- rasterFromXYZ(data.frame(var_env_proj_pres[,c(1,2)], Z = as.vector(pred[,i]), crs = crs(env_pres))
names(ras_pres) <- paste0("RDA_pres_", as.character(i))
Proj_pres[[i]] <- ras_pres
names(Proj_pres)[i] <- paste0("RDA", as.character(i))
}
}
# Mask with the range if supplied
if(!is.null(range)){
Proj_pres <- lapply(Proj_pres, function(x) mask(x, range))
}
}

```

```

# Returning projections for current climates for each RDA axis
return(Proj_pres = Proj_pres)
}
# genomic_offset()
# Function to predict genomic offset based on an RDA model (https://github.com/Capblancaq/RDA-landscape-genomics/blob/main/src/genomic\_offset.R)
# Credits to Capblancaq, T., & Forester, B. R. (2021). Redundancy analysis: A Swiss Army Knife for landscape genomics. Methods in Ecology and Evolution, 12(12), 2298-2309.
genomic_offset <- function(RDA, K, env_pres, env_fut, range = NULL, method = "loadings", scale_env, center_env){

# Mask with the range if supplied
if(!is.null(range)){
  env_pres <- mask(env_pres, range)
  env_fut <- mask(env_fut, range)
}
# Formatting and scaling environmental rasters for projection
var_env_proj_pres <- as.data.frame(scale(rasterToPoints(env_pres[[row.names(RDA$CCA$biplot)]][-c(1,2)],
center_env[row.names(RDA$CCA$biplot)], scale_env[row.names(RDA$CCA$biplot)]))
var_env_proj_fut <- as.data.frame(scale(rasterToPoints(env_fut[[row.names(RDA$CCA$biplot)]][-c(1,2)],
center_env[row.names(RDA$CCA$biplot)], scale_env[row.names(RDA$CCA$biplot)]))

# Predicting pixels genetic component based on the loadings of the variables
if(method == "loadings"){
  # Projection for each RDA axis
  Proj_pres <- list()
  Proj_fut <- list()
  Proj_offset <- list()
  for(i in 1:K){
    # Current climates
    ras_pres <- env_pres[[1]]
    ras_pres[!is.na(ras_pres)] <- as.vector(apply(var_env_proj_pres[,names(RDA$CCA$biplot[,i])], 1, function(x) sum(x *
RDA$CCA$biplot[,i])))
    names(ras_pres) <- paste0("RDA_pres_", as.character(i))
    Proj_pres[[i]] <- ras_pres
    names(Proj_pres)[i] <- paste0("RDA", as.character(i))
    # Future climates
    ras_fut <- env_fut[[1]]
    ras_fut[!is.na(ras_fut)] <- as.vector(apply(var_env_proj_fut[,names(RDA$CCA$biplot[,i])], 1, function(x) sum(x *
RDA$CCA$biplot[,i])))
    Proj_fut[[i]] <- ras_fut
    names(ras_fut) <- paste0("RDA_fut_", as.character(i))
    names(Proj_fut)[i] <- paste0("RDA", as.character(i))
    # Single-axis genetic offset
    Proj_offset[[i]] <- abs(Proj_pres[[i]] - Proj_fut[[i]])
    names(Proj_offset)[i] <- paste0("RDA", as.character(i))
  }
# Predicting pixels genetic component based on predict.RDA
if(method == "predict"){
  # Prediction with the RDA model and both sets of environments
  pred_pres <- predict(RDA, var_env_proj_pres[-c(1,2)], type = "lc")
  pred_fut <- predict(RDA, var_env_proj_fut[-c(1,2)], type = "lc")
  # List format
  Proj_offset <- list()
  Proj_pres <- list()
  Proj_fut <- list()
}
}

```

```

for(i in 1:K){
  # Current climates
  ras_pres <- rasterFromXYZ(data.frame(var_env_proj_pres[,c(1,2)], Z = as.vector(pred_pres[,i])), crs = crs(env_pres))
  names(ras_pres) <- paste0("RDA_pres_", as.character(i))
  Proj_pres[[i]] <- ras_pres
  names(Proj_pres)[i] <- paste0("RDA", as.character(i))
  # Future climates
  ras_fut <- rasterFromXYZ(data.frame(var_env_proj_pres[,c(1,2)], Z = as.vector(pred_fut[,i])), crs = crs(env_pres))
  names(ras_fut) <- paste0("RDA_fut_", as.character(i))
  Proj_fut[[i]] <- ras_fut
  names(Proj_fut)[i] <- paste0("RDA", as.character(i))
  # Single axis genetic offset
  Proj_offset[[i]] <- abs(Proj_pres[[i]] - Proj_fut[[i]])
  names(Proj_offset)[i] <- paste0("RDA", as.character(i))
}
# Weights based on axis eigen values
weights <- RDA$CCA$eig/sum(RDA$CCA$eig)
# Weighing the current and future adaptive indices based on the eigen values of the associated axes
Proj_offset_pres <- do.call(cbind, lapply(1:K, function(x) rasterToPoints(Proj_pres[[x]][,-c(1,2)])))
Proj_offset_fut <- do.call(cbind, lapply(1:K, function(x) rasterToPoints(Proj_fut[[x]][,-c(1,2)])))
Proj_offset_pres <- as.data.frame(do.call(cbind, lapply(1:K, function(x) Proj_offset_pres[,x]*weights[x])))
Proj_offset_fut <- as.data.frame(do.call(cbind, lapply(1:K, function(x) Proj_offset_fut[,x]*weights[x])))

# Predict a global genetic offset, incorporating the K first axes weighted by their eigenvalues
ras <- Proj_offset[[1]]
ras[!is.na(ras)] <- unlist(lapply(1:nrow(Proj_offset_pres), function(x) dist(rbind(Proj_offset_pres[x,], Proj_offset_fut[x,]),
method = "euclidean"))))
names(ras) <- "Global_offset"
Proj_offset_global <- ras

# Return projections for current and future climates for each RDA axis, prediction of genetic offset for each RDA axis, and
a global genetic offset
return(list(Proj_pres = Proj_pres, Proj_fut = Proj_fut, Proj_offset = Proj_offset, Proj_offset_global = Proj_offset_global,
weights = weights[1:K]))
}
# legend.col()
# credits to: https://aurelienmadouasse.wordpress.com/2012/01/13/legend-for-a-continuous-color-scale-in-r/
legend.col <- function(col, lev){
  opar <- par
  n <- length(col)
  bx <- par("usr")
  box.cx <- c(bx[2] + (bx[2] - bx[1]) / 1000,
             bx[2] + (bx[2] - bx[1]) / 1000 + (bx[2] - bx[1]) / 50)
  box.cy <- c(bx[3], bx[3])
  box.sy <- (bx[4] - bx[3]) / n
  xx <- rep(box.cx, each = 2)
  par(xpd = TRUE)
  for(i in 1:n){
    yy <- c(box.cy[1] + (box.sy * (i - 1)),
           box.cy[1] + (box.sy * (i)),
           box.cy[1] + (box.sy * (i)),
           box.cy[1] + (box.sy * (i - 1)))
    polygon(xx, yy, col = col[i], border = col[i])
  }
  par(new = TRUE)
}

```

```

plot(0, 0, type = "n",
     ylim = c(min(lev), max(lev)),
     yaxt = "n", ylab = "",
     xaxt = "n", xlab = "",
     frame.plot = FALSE)
axis(side = 4, las = 2, tick = FALSE, line = .25)
par <- opar}

```

2.2. Loading species location data

As mentioned above, the eggplant dataset used in this manual can be found at Dryad (<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.08kpr5c7>). It includes both the genetic and passport data; The data is also associated to the publication by Omondi et al. 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.17229>).

For more background on geospatial analysis, there are several guides and manuals. Here are two:

- <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/72785>
- <https://rspatial.org/raster/>

```

# Loading basic population passport data. The functions to read in your passport data depend on the passport data format
e.g. excel, csv or txt. Here we read in the data in csv format using the function read.csv() in R Utils package
met = read.csv("gps_ib.csv", header = TRUE) # Population information
head(met)

```

```

## G2P.Code Accession lat lon Country C_code Region
## 1 GPE031260 VI039419 26.20 88.56 Bangladesh BGD N. Bgd
## 2 GPE031280 VI039421 26.33 88.55 Bangladesh BGD N. Bgd

```

```

row.names(met) = met$G2P.Code
dim(met) # 331 genotypes

```

```
## [1] 331 7
```

```

#Coordinates of the sample accessions
library(dplyr) # used for data manipulation

```

```

coor = met%>% dplyr::select(lon, lat)
row.names(coor) = row.names(met)
head(coor)

```

```

##      lon lat
## GPE031260 88.56 26.20
## GPE031280 88.55 26.33

```

#To map your samples, you can use prior downloaded shape files of your study area (in this case, India and Bangladesh) or source map data from the rnaturalearth package through the function ne_countries()

```
library("rnaturalearth")
```

```

world_rnat <- ne_countries(scale = "medium", returnclass = "sf")
class(world_rnat)

```

```
## [1] "sf"      "data.frame"
```

```

#plot the region map and the sample locations
library(ggplot2)

```

```

ggplot(data = world_rnat) +
  geom_sf() +
  geom_point(data = met, aes(x=lon, y=lat), size=3, shape=21, fill= "red") +
  coord_sf(xlim = c(65, 100), ylim = c(5, 35), expand = FALSE)

```


#Prepare the shape files of the study region

```
library(geodata)
```

```
library(sf)
```

```
ib_sv = geodata::gadm(c("India", "Bangladesh"), level=0, path = "data/", version="latest", resolution=1) #Gives a
spatvector of r bound shapes for the countries specified
```

```
indbng = sf::st_as_sf(ib_sv) # Converts spatvector to an sf or dataframe object suitable for downstream analysis and
plotting
```

```
plot(indbng) # To see the shape file
```

2.3. Sources of environmental data

Given the wide range of abiotic and biotic factors that can influence selection, it becomes imperative to carefully assess the factors that hold the most significant relevance and possess the strongest potential for offering comprehensive explanations. Usually, knowledge about the most significant environmental factors is not known at the onset of a study. So far, landscape genomic studies have applied abiotic data predominantly. Studies can obtain environmental data through in situ measurements, remote sensing, or spatial interpolation. Large interpolation-based, georeferenced environmental databases such as WorldClim are open-access and user-friendly. They are neat and eliminate the need to gather additional environmental information on-site. These data have been made available by the collaborative efforts of international groups focused on obtaining, analyzing, storing, and distributing environmental data on a global scale.

Imagine the potential of incorporating diverse environmental data in your research. Most studies on abiotic factors have primarily considered climate factors in their analyses of genetic-environment association (GEA). Studies have also considered topography and soil factors, although to a lesser extent because less data is available on these environmental factors compared to climate data. The best strategy is to integrate diverse environmental data to comprehensively assess the multifaceted nature of local adaptation.

Finding a single data source that fulfills all requirements in terms of spatial and temporal coverage is highly unlikely; hence, there is an even greater need to use a collection of diverse datasets to effectively capture the dynamic nature of the environment across different locations and periods. Most data are usually available in raster formats. Integrating different data in your analysis might require processing and combining data from various sources. We will review the different ways of processing the environmental data to make it usable in the case study in this manual.

Here are some environmental data sources.

Climate data

- WorldClim <https://worldclim.org/data> (Fick and Hijmans 2017)
- Environmental Rasters for Ecological Modeling (ENVIREM) <https://envirem.github.io/> (Title and Bemmels 2018)
- Climatologies at high resolution for the earth's land surface areas (CHELSA) <https://chelsa-climate.org/> (Karger et al., 2017)
- CHIRPS <https://www.chc.ucsb.edu/data/chirps> (Funk et al., 2015)
- CHIRTS <https://www.chc.ucsb.edu/data/chirtsdaily> (Funk et al., 2019)

Soil

- Soilgrids <https://soilgrids.org/> (Hengl et al., 2014, 2017)

The choice of database largely depends on the spatial and temporal scale required for the organism in the study. For instance, annual plants would need a lesser spatial resolution than migratory birds, and annual plants would also require a higher time scale than long-lived trees. Several studies have applied the WorldClim database. However, other databases such as CHELSA and ENVIREM have significantly improved by introducing indices, rather than raw environmental variables, that summarize precise physiological processes (e.g., thermal thresholds and potential evapotranspiration models to infer heat/drought stress). They also present spatially high-resolution climate data to predict regional and micro-habitat levels accurately.

2.4. Processing environmental data

This manual will use the publicly available climate data from WorldClim (<https://worldclim.org/data0>) (Fick and Hijmans 2017) and soil data (*Soilgrid*). Download and store the raster files to a file on your PC. Make separate files to store the climate and soil rasters. Preferably, you should store files with a similar pattern in naming to enable easy reading of files in R using the R base function *list.files*).

As an option, the *geodata* package has functions that allow direct download of data from WorldClim and Soilgrids (<https://files.isric.org>) (Hengl et al., 2014, 2017) databases. Note that only the global functions of the *geodata* package will enable you to specify the resolution of the data you want when downloading the WorldClim data.

The choice of spatial resolution depends on the organism of study. Still, we would like to say that it may depend on the georeferencing accuracy of the samples. For instance, we chose a moderate resolution of 2.5 min because there might be inaccuracies when georeferencing using passport data describing sampling locations. You could use a finer resolution of 30 arc-sec if you obtained more accurate coordinate information using a GPS device at the collection point. We also downloaded soil data for a depth of 15–30 cm, considering the approximate soil depth of eggplant roots. Data for other soil depths are also available and can be chosen considering the study species.

Loading environmental rasters and extracting environmental data

In this step, we will import the global environmental data into the R environment for further processing. The environmental data files were downloaded from the respective databases and stored in the PC. Alternatively, to save time and storage space in your computer, you can use the **geodata** package (Hijmans et al., 2023) that facilitates access to climate, elevation, soil and administrative boundary data. However, the climate data is only limited to the WorldClim data.

2.4.1. Import climate data from WorldClim (2.5 min resolution)

As mentioned, this manual will use the publicly available climate data from WorldClim representing a wide range of ecologically meaningful climate variables related to temperature, temperature variability, precipitation, and precipitation variability (<https://worldclim.org/data0>) (Fick and Hijmans 2017). This data is widely used in scientific publications and is straightforward to manage in R. Start Script 2.4.1.

```
# Loading the climate data from WorldClim (2.5 min resolution)
library(raster)

# Loading the main bioclim data from WorldClim (bio1-19)
Wclim=list.files(path='D:/DATA/Climate data/wc2.1_2.5m_bio', pattern='.tif', full.names = TRUE)

Wclims = raster::stack(Wclim)
names(Wclims)=c("AMT_1", "MTWaQ_10", "MTCoQ_11", "AP_12", "PWeM_13", "PDrM_14", "PSe_15", "PWeQ_16", "PDrQ_17", "PWaQ_18", "PCoQ_19", "MDiR_2", "Iso_3", "TSe_4", "MTWaM_5", "MiTCoQ_6", "TAR_7", "MTWeQ_8", "MTDrQ_9")

# Extra Wclim variables (2.5 min resolution)
# Minimum temperature (°C)
tmin_files = list.files("D:/DATA/Climate data/wc2.1_2.5m_tmin/", pattern=".tif", full.names = TRUE)
tmins = raster::stack(tmin_files)
tmin = mean(tmins)
rm(tmin_files, tmins)
```

```

# Maximum temperature (°C)
tmax_files = list.files("D:/DATA/Climate data/wc2.1_2.5m_tmax/", pattern = ".tif", full.names = TRUE)
tmaxs = raster::stack(tmax_files)
tmax = mean (tmaxs)
rm(tmax_files, tmaxs)

# Average temperature (°C)
tavg_files = list.files("D:/DATA/Climate data/wc2.1_2.5m_tavg/", pattern = ".tif", full.names = TRUE)
tavg = raster::stack(tavg_files)
tavg = mean (tavg)
rm(tavg_files, tavg)

# Solar radiation (kJ m-2 day-1)
srad_files = list.files("D:/DATA/Climate data/wc2.1_2.5m_srad/", pattern = ".tif", full.names = TRUE)
srad = raster::stack(srad_files)
srad = mean (srad)
rm(srad_files, srad)

# Wind speed (m s-1)
wind_files = list.files("D:/DATA/Climate data/wc2.1_2.5m_wind/", pattern = ".tif", full.names = TRUE)
winds = raster::stack(wind_files)
wind = mean (winds)
rm(wind_files, winds)

# Water vapor pressure (kPa)
vapr_files = list.files("D:/DATA/Climate data/wc2.1_2.5m_vapr/", pattern = ".tif", full.names = TRUE)
vapr = raster::stack(vapr_files)
vapr = mean (vapr)
rm(vapr_files, vapr)

# Stack together the extra WorldClim variables files
wcl_extra = raster::stack(tmin, tmax, srad, vapr, wind)
names(wcl_extra) = c ("tmin", "tmax", "srad", "vapr", "wind")
writeRaster(wcl_extra, "wcl_extra.tif")

```

Since all the WorldClim data have the same resolution and extent, we can stack them together and then crop them to the size of the study area to make computation easier and faster in the following step.

```

# Stack together all the WorldClim climate data
Clims = raster::stack(Wclims, wcl_extra) # Stacking rasters
Clims = raster::crop(Clims, indbng) # Cropping using the shapefile

# Elevation
Elev = raster("D:/DATA/Climate data/wc2.1_2.5m_elev/wc2.1_2.5m_elev.tif")
Elev = crop(Elev, indbng)
names(Elev) = c(Elev)

```

2.4.2. Import soil data from Soilgrids

Soilgrids is the most comprehensive and detailed georeferenced soil database <https://soilgrids.org/> (Hengl et al., 2014, 2017). This dataset will be imported into R to obtain soil parameters associated to location data.

#Soil data was obtained from ISRIC soil grids (<https://files.isric.org/soilgrids/latest/data/>). The data resolution is 250m. The data is available in different soil depths. Fifteen to thirty-centimeter soil depth was chosen for this analysis, considering the eggplant's approximate root depth.

```
soil = list.files( path='D:/LANDSCAPE_GENOMICS/Gap analysis/soil data', pattern='.tif', full.names = TRUE)
```

```
soils = raster::stack(soil)
```

```
names(soils) = c('cec', 'clay', 'nitrogen', 'ocd', 'ocs', 'pH', 'sand', 'silt', 'soc')
```

```
# Crop the soil rasters to the study area only
```

```
soils = raster::crop(soils, indbng)
```

```
plot(soils[[3]])# Nitrogen raster for instance
```


NOTE: As can be observed in the plot, there are instances when soil variables values for some points are missing (e.g., due to a lack of lab information that could be extrapolated for some areas). Check carefully for missing data points after extracting the raster values. In this case, you may need to filter out some samples if you won't lose too many. Some variables may also show persistent missing values or the same values for several samples. You may consider removing such variables from the environmental variable data frame.

2.4.3. Combine environmental data sets

In this exercise, climate, soil raster, and elevation data are combined to make a full set of environmental predictor rasters. Before this, check that the rasters have the same extent and resolution to enable stacking.

```
# Change soil rasters to the same resolution as climate data
```

```
soils = raster::resample(soils, Clims)
```

```
res(soils)
```

```
## [1] 0.04166667 0.04166667
```

```
res(Clims)
```

```
## [1] 0.04166667 0.04166667
```

```

# Combine all the environmental rasters
Env_ras = raster::stack(Clims, soils)
names(Env_ras)

## [1] "AMT_1" "MTWaQ_10" "MTCoQ_11" "AP_12" "PWeM_13" "PDrM_14"
## [7] "PSe_15" "PWeQ_16" "PDrQ_17" "PWaQ_18" "PCoQ_19" "MDiR_2"
## [13] "Iso_3" "TSe_4" "MTWaM_5" "MiTCoQ_6" "TAR_7" "MTWeQ_8"
## [19] "MTDrQ_9" "tmin" "tmax" "srad" "vapr" "wind"
## [25] "cec" "clay" "nitrogen" "ocd" "ocs" "pH"
## [31] "sand" "silt" "soc"

```

Once all the environmental rasters are ready, we can now extract environmental variable values from the raster using the GPS coordinates using the `extract()` function in the raster package.

```

Envvars = raster::extract(Env_ras, coor)
Elevs = raster::extract(Elev, coor)

# Combine the environmental data (climate and soil) with the elevation data
All_envvars = cbind(Envvars, Elevs)

# Give the same row names as the passport data
rownames(All_envvars) = rownames(met)
View(All_envvars)

# Store the extracted environmental data in the working directory
write.csv(All_envvars, "All-envvars.csv")

# Remove NA variables and samples. Some data sets miss data at some points, and this brings about NA for some variables
and samples
Envvars1 = All_envvars[-c(83,84,93,101,102,229,311),] #7 samples removed

dim(Envvars1)
## [1] 324 34

```

All the environmental variables seem fine, but we have filtered out seven samples presenting NA values, especially for the soil variables. We finally have 324 samples remaining and 34 environmental variables (climate and soil). Since we removed some samples with missing values for some environmental variables, we edited passport data according to the final environmental variables dataframe.

```

met1 = subset(met, rownames(met) %in% rownames(Envvars1))
dim(met1)
## [1] 324 7

# Combine the passport data and the environmental variables
Alldata = cbind(met1, Envvars1)
View(Alldata)

# You may want to save the files in your directory for later use
write.csv(Alldata, "Meta_envdata.csv", row.names = FALSE)

```

2.5. Environmental data variable reduction

Numerous environmental factors as predictors in traditional models necessitate reducing them initially to prevent collinearity issues, which can distort model fit and interpretation of results. Principles such as pairwise correlation, variation inflation factor, or principal component analysis (PCA) can guide the variable reduction

process. LSG studies have applied different principles (Dauphin et al., 2023). Another strategy involves using species distribution modeling (SDM) to identify the most relevant environmental predictors driving local adaptation. SDM, or environmental (ecological) niche models or habitat distribution models, uses computer algorithms to analyze environmental data and predict species distribution across geographic space and time. Excluding correlated factors may require additional information, like expert insight on potentially selective predictors or species data, to retain the most pertinent factors. For a thorough review of collinearity (variable reduction), see Dormann et al. (2013).

Some studies include variable selection as a crucial step, when feasible, within the selected analytical framework to assess the predictive capability of potential predictors (Dauphin et al., 2023). Variable selection involves employing backward or forward stepwise selection techniques to identify and retain a model's most informative and largely independent predictors, thereby mitigating the risk of overfitting. The decision regarding the optimal model and the variables you can retain is typically guided by criteria such as Akaike's information criterion, Bayesian information criterion, or adjusted R-squared.

2.5.1. Apply the variance inflation factor

For this manual, we will apply the variance inflation factor (VIF) to reduce our environmental variable and to check multicollinearity. Ideally, a VIF threshold below ten is recommended, but lower values, though more conservative, are even more desirable.

```
# A function to effect VIF reduction
library(fuzzySim)
env_pruning <- function(X = NULL, vif.thr = NULL) {
  cat("\n"); cat("When using this function, please cite:"); cat("\n")
  cat("[1] https://besjournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/2041-210X.12372")
  cat("\n"); cat("\n")
  res <- list()
  env_vif <- multicol(vars = X)
  while (length(which(env_vif$VIF > vif.thr)) >= 1) {
    t <- rownames(env_vif)[1]
    t <- which(colnames(X) == t)
    X <- X[, -t]
    env_vif <- multicol(vars = X)
    print(env_vif); cat("\n")
  }
  res[[1]] <- X
  res[[2]] <- cor(X)
  names(res) <- c(paste0("Pruned environmental data set (VIF<", vif.thr, ")"), "Correlation matrix")
  return(res)
}
# VIF reduction using a threshold of 2
envqc <- env_pruning(X = Envars1, vif.thr = 2)

# Check the correlation
library(corrplot)
corrplot(
  envqc$`Correlation matrix`,
  order = "original", type = "upper", diag=T, tl.cex = 1,
  tl.col = "black",
  addCoef.col = "white",
  number.cex = 0.6, number.font = 0.8)

```



```
# Combine the selected variables with the passport data to keep information flow You may also want to save the file in
your directory
env_vif = Alldata[,c("G2P.Code", "Accession", "lat", "lon", "Country", "C_code", "Region", "PDrM_14", "PSe_15", "PCoQ_19",
"nitrogen", "silt", "clay", "ocs" )]
```

```
# Save the selected environmental variable data frame to the working directory
write.csv(env_vif, "Meta_envqc.csv", row.names = FALSE)
```

Using the `hist_env()` function, we can determine the variables' distribution frequencies (histograms). It is important to allow visual checks for normal distributions of the samples for each variable.

```
# X: a data.frame object with rows corresponding to individuals and columns to environmental variables
# The function returns the histograms of the variables provided
hist_env <- function(X = NULL) {
  X <- as.data.frame(X)
  for (i in 1:ncol(X)) {
    if (i == 2) {
      op <- par(ask=TRUE)
    }
    hist(X[, i], main="", xlab=colnames(X)[i])
    title(colnames(X)[i])
  }
  par(op)
}
```

This will show us the distribution of the samples for the retained variables. Run the line as many times as the number of variables to obtain the histogram for all the variables
hist_env(envqc\$`Pruned environmental data set (VIF<2)`)

NOTE: Looking at the histograms, several environmental variables would require normalization for the downstream analysis. For instance, the histogram for the distribution of precipitation of the coldest quarter (PCoQ_19) shows that most samples experience below 250 mm, with some samples falling in the high ranges above 1,500 mm. Such a vast temperature difference scenario is expected to result in adaptation by the local population.

2.5.2. Principal component analysis of the environmental data

We can also perform a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using the environmental variables to show how the accessions (referred to as populations in the R scripts) will likely be separated into groups depending on the selected environmental variables. This also helps support our hypothesis of differential environmental characteristics of the accessions in the study.

```
# PCA of the environmental data
library(factoextra)

pca_env=prcomp(env_vif[,-c(1:7)], scale. = TRUE)

# Plot environmental data PCA
fviz_pca_biplot(pca_env, geom=c("point", "text"),
  label = "var",
  # alpha.var ="contrib"
  col.var = "contrib",
  fill.ind = env_vif$Region, #defined populations
  col.ind = "black",
  pointshape = 21, pointsize = 3,
  palette = "Dark2")+
labs(fill = "Population", color = "Contrib") #Change legend title
```


NOTE: The environmental PCA plot shows the grouping of accessions grouped by geographic area and the contribution of environmental factors to differentiating them. Other tests, such as mantle tests, can also test the correlation between environmental distance (environmental differences) and geographic distances. Silt, precipitation of the coldest quarter, and soil organic carbon seem to be the environmental factors that contribute most to differentiating the Accessions. These are the environmental factors to keep an eye on in the genotype-environment association analysis in the following sections.

3. Import and population structure of genomic data

Aims:

- Processing and importing genomic data
- Population structure analysis

3.1. Generating genomic data

In many studies, single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) are the choice makers because of their abundance across genomes. They can be easily standardized among laboratories, and their flanking sequences can be quickly and directly queried in public databases, enabling association with known locations and functions. SNPs are obtained through whole genome sequencing. So far, whole genome sequencing is rare because of the cost implications. Alternatively, targeting a subset of the genome has facilitated the genotyping of large numbers of SNPs while reducing cost. Many methods have been used (e.g., RAD-seq, GBS, and SPET). Genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) is an attractive complexity reduction method that offers a simple, robust, low-cost, and high-throughput method for genotyping in both model and non-model species. Further details on the methods are beyond this manual's scope, and the choice will depend on the organism, the sequencing depth required, and the cost.

3.2. Import genomic data to R

Our genomic data is in numerical format after converting the genomic data VCF file into a numerical genotype dataframe. To do this we first converted the VCF into a 'genind' format and the finally the 'genind' into a dataframe as shown in the script 3.2.1 below.

Start of Script 3.2.1.

```
library(vcfR)
## *****   *** vcfR   ***   *****
## This is vcfR 1.15.0
## browseVignettes('vcfR') # Documentation
## citation('vcfR') # Citation
## *****   *****   *****   *****

vcf = read.vcfR("IndBng_SPET.vcf", verbose = FALSE)
vcf #331 samples, 4,308 SNPs with no missing data

## ***** Object of Class vcfR *****
## 331 samples
## 13 CHROMs
## 4,308 variants
## Object size: 13.2 Mb
## 0 percent missing data
## *****   *****   *****

# You can check the elements of your vcf file using @ after the name e.g., geno@
gnd = vcfR2genind(vcf)

library(adegenet)

gen_df = genind2df(gnd)
View(gen_df)

# Sample passport data
```

```

env_vif = read.csv("Meta_envqc.csv")
row.names(env_vif) = env_vif$G2P.Code

# Coordinates of the sample accessions
library(dplyr)

coor = env_vif%>% dplyr::select(lon, lat)
row.names(coor) = row.names(env_vif)
head(coor)

##      lon lat
## GPE031260 88.56 26.20
## GPE031280 88.55 26.33

# Coordinates to spatialpoints dataframe
library(sp)
sp_crd <- SpatialPointsDataFrame(coords = coor, data = env_vif, proj4string = CRS("+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84
+ellps=WGS84 +towgs84=0,0,0"))

# Plot to see if the orientation is proper
plot(sp_crd)

```

Since we filtered out some of the samples due to missing data in the previous section, removing them from the genomic data set is also necessary. We do this by subsetting the genomic data with the environmental data, as we did with the original passport data file.

```

gen_df = subset(gen_df, rownames(gen_df) %in% env_vif$G2P.Code)
dim(gen_df) #Reduces the sample number from the original 331 to 324

## [1] 324 4308

# Edit the data appropriately for following step analysis, e.g., in redundancy analysis (accepts only 0,1,2 and 9-NA)
gen_df[gen_df == "11"] = 1
gen_df[gen_df == "00"] = 0
gen_df[gen_df == "01"] = 2
gen_df[gen_df == "10"] = 2
gen_df[is.na(gen_df)] = 9
View(gen_df)
write.csv(gen_df, "gen_df.csv", row.names = TRUE) # store in the working directory

```

Before proceeding, we need to check if the order of the individuals in the genomic data and the environmental data is the same.

```

# In our case, the order of the elements is the same
# you could use a base R function identical()
identical(row.names(gen_df), row.names(env_vif))

## [1] TRUE

# If not, you can use the following code to sort the environmental data set as a function of the IDs order in the genomic
data set
gen_df <- gen_df[match(row.names(gen_df), row.names(env_vif)),]

# We can proceed to add more information to the genind object, e.g., populations, individual names, and the passport
data as strata
ind = as.factor(env_vif$G2P.Code) #individual ID

```

```

site = as.factor(env_vif$Region) #site ID

gnd = df2genind(gen_df,
  ploidy = 1,
  ind.names = ind,
  pop = site,
  strata = env_vif[,c(1:7)],
  sep = "")

gnd
## /// GENIND OBJECT ///////////
## // 324 individuals; 4,308 loci; 14,109 alleles; size: 20.6 Mb

```

3.3. Individual ancestry coefficients

For the estimation of Individual Ancestry Coefficients similar to STRUCTURE and ADMIXTURE. STRUCTURE and ADMIXTURE assumptions include the absence of genetic drift and Hardy–Weinberg and linkage equilibrium in ancestral populations. Sparse Nonnegative Matrix Factorization (sNMF) was more appropriate for dealing with inbred lineages. sNMF enabled the estimation of homozygote and heterozygote frequencies and avoided Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium assumptions. The cross-entropy criterion indicated better predictive results for sNMF than for ADMIXTURE (Frichot and François 2015). You can use *impute()* to predict Ancestry Coefficients for missing values. Other methods of genetic structure analysis include DAPC, PCA, and TessR.

```

# sNMF accepts geno/lfmm objects. In this case, we convert the genlight object to geno/lfmm using gi2gl function in dartR package

```

```

library(dartR)

```

```

gnl = gi2gl(gnd) #To genlight

```

```

# Conversion of the genlight into geno. This produces a geno and an lfmm object in the working directory. In the following sections, we will use the Geno file for the sNMF analysis and the lfmm file for the LFMM analysis in the genotype-environment analysis

```

```

gl2geno(gnl, outfile = "geno", outpath = getwd(), verbose = NULL)

```

```

# Run sNMF STRUCTURE like population structure analysis

```

```

library(LEA)

```

```

obj.snmf = snmf("./geno.geno",

```

```

  K = 1:10,

```

```

  project = "new",

```

```

  repetitions = 20,

```

```

  entropy=TRUE,

```

```

  ploidy = 2,

```

```

  alpha = 100, # A numeric value corresponding to the sNMF regularization parameter. The results can depend on the value of this parameter, especially for small data sets

```

```

  iterations = 200)

```

```

# Plot cross-entropy criterion of all runs of the project. This plot helps us identify the number of clusters most likely in our population

```

```

plot(obj.snmf, cex = 2, col = "blue", pch = 19)

```


For this analysis, we will use K=4. The cross-entropy seems to flatten after K=4. We also consider the resulting output for a side analysis using STRUCTURE software that indicated optimal K at 4.

```
# Get the cross-entropy value for each run at your selected K
ce <- cross.entropy(obj.snmf, K= 4)
ce

# Select the run with the lowest cross-entropy value for K = ?
best <- which.min(ce) # The best run is #4 at k=5
best

## [1] 3

qmatrix = Q(obj.snmf, K = 4, run = best)

q_mat = qmatrix
colnames(q_mat) <- paste0("P", 1:4)
head(q_mat)

##      P1    P2    P3    P4
## [1,] 0.240726000 0.000099982 0.759074 9.99820e-05
## [2,] 0.446405000 0.100006000 0.453489 9.99911e-05
## [6,] 0.216780000 0.000099982 0.783020 9.99820e-05

# Add Ancestry Coefficients to the passport data and selected environmental data
met1 = cbind(env_vif, q_mat)
head(met1)
```



```

### # A tibble: 324 × 7
##   P1   P2   P3   P4 individual region order
##   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <chr>   <chr>   <chr>   <chr>
## 1 0.241 0.000100 0.759 0.000100 GPE031260 N. Bgd GPE031260
## 2 0.446 0.100 0.453 0.000100 GPE031280 N. Bgd GPE031280
## # i 314 more rows
write.csv(q_df, "snmf_k3_qmat.csv", row.names = F)

library(tidyr)
# We now transform the data to a "long" format for plotting
# The population column names get their column and the ancestry proportions (q) get their column
q_df_long <- q_df %>%
# Transform the data to a "long" format to plot proportions
  pivot_longer(cols = starts_with("P"), names_to = "pop", values_to = "q")

q_df_long

### # A tibble: 1,296 × 5
##   individual region order  pop    q
##   <chr>   <chr> <chr> <chr> <dbl>
## 1 GPE031260 N. Bgd GPE031260 P1  0.241
## 2 GPE031260 N. Bgd GPE031260 P2  0.000100
## # i 1,287 more rows

# Order the individuals for plotting. Since we are interested in matching the data, we will order the individuals by ancestry
proportions
q_df_ordered <- q_df_long %>%
# Assign the population assignment according to the max q value (ancestry proportion) and include the assignment
probability of the population assignment
  group_by(individual) %>% # You can also group by your assigned populations ("Regions" in our data)
    mutate(likely_assignment = pop[which.max(q)],
           assignment_prob = max(q)) %>%
# Arrange the data set by the Ancestry coefficients
  arrange(likely_assignment, assignment_prob) %>%
# This ensures that the factor levels for the individuals follow the ordering we just did
  ungroup() %>%
  mutate(individual = forcats::fct_inorder(factor(individual)))

q_df_ordered

## Store the ordered q matrix dataframe
write.csv(q_df_ordered, "qmat_df_ordered.csv", row.names = FALSE)

# Plot the ordered q_df
q_palette <- RColorBrewer::brewer.pal(4, "Paired")
p1 = ggplot(q_df_ordered) +
  geom_col(aes(x = individual, y = q, fill = pop), width = 1) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = q_palette, labels = c("P1", "P2", "P3", "P4")) +
# Scale_fill_viridis_d() +
  labs(fill = "pop", title = "Ancestry matrix", x = "Individuals", y = "Ancestry coefficients") +
  theme_minimal() +
# Some formatting details to make it pretty
  theme(legend.position = "none",
        panel.background = element_blank(),
        axis.title.y = element_text(size = rel(1.3), angle = 90),

```

```
axis.title.x = element_text(size = rel(1.3)),
axis.ticks.length.x = unit(-.2, "cm"),
axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, vjust = 0.3, hjust=1, size = 5))
```

p1

We can further sort out the Q matrix by the assigned populations and then plot the population bar graph. The sorted graph clearly shows the structure overview in each population.

```
# Sorting Q matrix
q_df_sort = q_df %>% arrange(region)

# Estimating Individual Admixture Proportions from NGS data

barplot(t(q_df_sort[,1:4]),col= q_palette ,border = NA, space = 0 ,
        xlab = "Individuals",
        ylab = "Admixture coefficients",
        main = "Ancestry matrix", horiz = FALSE,
        names.arg = q_df_sort$region, cex.names=0.5, las = 2)
```


We can also plot the population structure on the map to clearly show the diversity distribution in our study area. The individuals' admix ancestries are represented as pie charts using the function `make.admix.pie.plot()` from the R package `construct`.

```
# Admixture pie plot
library(construct)# To make the admixture pies
library(maps) # For map information database

q_palette <- RColorBrewer::brewer.pal(4, "Paired") # We assign the same color as the barplot for consistency
coord = met1%>% dplyr::select(lon, lat) # Coordinates of our samples
indban = maps::map(xlim = range(coord[,1]) + c(-2,2),
                  ylim = range(coord[,2]) + c(-2,2),
                  col="navyblue")

plot(indban, xlab = "Longitude", ylab = "Latitude", type = "n")

# You can add map text to give your readers an orientation of your map
map.text("world", "ind", add = TRUE, cex = 1)

maps::map(xlim = range(coord[,1]) + c(-2,2), ylim = range(coord[,2]) + c(-2,2), col="navyblue", add = TRUE)

# Add the admixture pie plot
make.admix.pie.plot(admix.proportions = as.matrix(q_df[,c(1:4)]),
                   coords = coord, layer.colors = q_palette, radii = 2,
                   add = TRUE)
```


NOTE: The population structure analysis identified four clusters (K=4). The geographic distribution of the population structure plotted as pie charts on the India-Bangladesh maps clearly shows a directional distinction of the populations based on the grouping by regions. Accessions in Northeast India and a few from the East India populations cluster together with the Bangladesh populations. East and Northeast India regions comprised individuals modeled as highly admixed compared to the other areas.

3.4. Principal component analysis

Principal component analysis (PCA) is an important method that has widely been used to determine the population structure based on genomic data. Using PCA, we can project the genotypes onto spaces after reducing the data to smaller dimensions (principal components) (Elhaik, 2024). The visualization of the genotype onto the space enables identification of the samples that likely share origin or ancestry. In the following scripts we have applied PCA to corroborate the Structure analysis in showing the population clustering of our samples. Start of Script 3.4.1.

```
# Principal component analysis

library(adegenet)
library(scales)
library(RColorBrewer)

gnl # Genomic data as a genlight object

# Setting the ploidy
ploidy(gnl) <- as.integer(1)

# Adding strata to the genlight object
strata(gnl) <- data.frame(met1)

# Set population to Genetic_Cluster
setPop(gnl) <- ~Region
gnl

## /// GENLIGHT OBJECT ///
## // 324 genotypes, 4,308 binary SNPs, size: 1.6 Mb

# PCA using glPca() function from adegenet package

pca_gnl <- glPca(gnl, nf = 4) # nf = NULL if you do not want to select the number of axes to be retained
barplot(100*pca_gnl$eig/sum(pca_gnl$eig), col = heat.colors(50), main="PCA Eigenvalues") # Looks like 2 or 3 explain
most of the variance
title(ylab="Percent of variance \n explained", line = 2)
title(xlab="Eigenvalues", line = 1)
```

PCA Eigenvalues

The first three PCAs explain a larger part of the variance with PC1 explaining by far the greatest proportion.

```
# To see variance explained
var.expl <- 100*pca_gnl$eig/sum(pca_gnl$eig)
var.expl

pca_gnl.scores <- as.data.frame(pca_gnl$scores)
pca_gnl.scores$pop <- pop(gnl)

# See order to assign colors
levels(pca_gnl.scores$pop)
# Colors
pop.col = c("#A6CEE3", "#33A02C", "#A6CEE3", "#33A02C", "#1F78B4", "#A6CEE3", "#1F78B4") # Colour chosen from
population structure bar plot population colours

p <- ggplot(pca_gnl.scores, aes(x=PC1, y=PC2, colour=pop, fill=pop))
p <- p + geom_point(shape=21, colour="black", size=4) + theme_classic()
p <- p + scale_colour_manual(values = pop.col, aesthetics = c("fill", "colour"), na.value = "grey90",

limits = c("N. Bgd", "C. Bgd", "S. Bgd", "NE. Ind", "E. Ind", "S. Ind", "C. Ind"), name="Populations")
p <- p + stat_ellipse(level = 0.95, size = 0.6)
p <- p + labs(x= "PC1 (16.5%)", y = "PC2 (4.2%)") # Figures from var.expl
p <- p + geom_hline(yintercept = 0, size=0.1, colour = "grey")
p <- p + geom_vline(xintercept = 0, size=0.1, colour = "grey")
p <- p + theme(panel.border = element_rect(fill = NA))
p
```


NOTE: The PCA clustering corresponded to the population structure analysis results. The first two PC axes explained 16.5% and 4.2% of the variation, respectively, and Southern and Central India populations differed from the other populations on the first PC. Usually, PCA and population structure analysis are used complementarily to assess the diversity among the samples.

4. Landscape genomics to identify adaptive alleles

Aims

- Identifying single-nucleotide polymorphisms under selection using selected environmental variables
- Gene annotation using a reference genome

4.1. Identifying SNPs under selection using environmental variables

Identifying SNPs under selection provides insight into the mechanisms underlying local adaptation. The loci can be identified through genotype-environment association (GEA) (sometimes referred to as Environmental Association Analysis (EAA) (Rellstab et al., 2015). The other possibility is through differentiation outlier methods, which identify loci with strong allele frequency differences among populations. GEA is more promising because it is based on the association between the genetic data and the environmental variables hypothesized to drive the selection. Moreover, GEA also offers the option of using individual-based (as opposed to population-based) sampling. Including environmental variables can improve power and allow for the detection of selective events that result in weak, multilocus genetic differentiation among populations (Rellstab et al., 2015). GEA includes multivariate and univariate approaches.

4.2. Genetic-environment association analysis

There are different type of approaches to associate genomic data with environmental data in Genetic-Environment Association (GEA) analysis. They can be grouped in multivariate and univariate approaches.

Multivariate approaches

- Analyzes many loci simultaneously.
- More suited to large datasets of hundreds of individuals and thousands of markers.
- They are more effective for detecting multilocus selection since they consider how groups of markers covary in response to environmental predictors (Rellstab et al., 2015). This is important because many adaptive processes are expected to result in weak, multilocus molecular signatures due to selection on standing genetic variation, which is recent (i.e. contemporary selection that has not yet led to allele fixation).
- Includes Redundancy Analysis (RDA), Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA), Generalized Dissimilarity Modelling, Multivariate Linear Mixed Models (mvLMM), and others. The appropriate approach depends on the specific research questions, the data's nature, and the available computational resources.

Univariate approaches

- Test one locus and one predictor variable at a time, unlike multivariate methods.
- While they perform well, they can produce elevated false positive rates without correction using false discovery rate (Benjamini and Hochberg 1995) or Bonferroni correction.
- Includes generalized linear models, latent factor mixed models (LFMM), and non-parametric approaches (e.g., partial Mantel).
- Selecting the appropriate method depends on the data structure, the genetic and environmental data, and the specific research questions.

For comparing the performance of the GEA methods using published simulations of multilocus selection please refer to Forester et al. (2018). In general, they found that Random Forest performed poorly for GEA. Univariate GEAs performed better but had low detection rates for loci under weak selection. Constrained ordinations, particularly Redundancy Analysis (RDA), showed a superior combination of low false-positive and high true-

positive rates across all levels of selection. These results were robust across the demographic histories, sampling designs, sample sizes, and weak population structures they tested.

Here, we focus on RDA (multivariate) and LFMM (univariate). We will finally combine the detection outcomes to make our outlier genetic data set. We will also look keenly at the overlapping loci between the two approaches. The main challenge of GEA and other outlier detection methods is that they may result in high rates of false positives. This means significant associations that are not casual. The main reason for the false positives is that geographic and demographic processes can lead to patterns that mimic those observed due to selection. In our analysis, we control the population structure to reduce false positives. Controlling for population structure is possible for most GEA methods.

4.2.1 SNP data upload

Here we will upload again genomic data just like was done in section 3.2.

```
# Load the SNP dataset
```

```
library(vcfR)
```

```
## *****   *** vcfR   ***   *****
```

```
## This is vcfR 1.15.0
```

```
## browseVignettes('vcfR') # Documentation
```

```
## citation('vcfR') # Citation
```

```
## *****   *****   *****   *****
```

```
vcf_filt = read.vcfR("Filtered.vcf", verbose = FALSE)
```

```
# You can check the elements of your vcf file using @ after the name  
vcf_filt@fix #324 samples, 4,308 SNPs with no missing data
```

```
# Make a genind
```

```
gnd_filt = vcfR2genind(vcf_filt)
```

```
## Loading required namespace: adegenet
```

```
library(adegenet)
```

```
gendf_filt = genind2df(gnd_filt)
```

```
gendf_filt[1:5, 1:5]
```

```
##      SO_23551 SO_662171 SO_2016898 SO_2027177 SO_3159570
```

```
## GPE031260   11    00    00    00    01
```

```
## GPE031280   10    01    00    00    01
```

```
## GPE031360   00   <NA>    00    00    00
```

```
# Edit the data appropriately for the following step analysis, e.g., in redundancy analysis (accepts only 0,1,2 and 9 for NA)
```

```
gendf_filt[gendf_filt == "11"] = 1
```

```
gendf_filt[gendf_filt == "00"] = 0
```

```
gendf_filt[gendf_filt == "01"] = 2
```

```
gendf_filt[gendf_filt == "10"] = 2
```

```
gendf_filt[is.na(gendf_filt)] = 9
```

```
# Convert the dataframe to numeric for use in GEA
```

```
gendf_filt[] = lapply(gendf_filt, as.numeric)
```

```

Write.csv(gendf_filt, "gendf_filt.csv", row.names = TRUE) # store in the working directory

### Create LFMM file
library(dartR)
gnl_filt = gi2gl(gnd_filt) # to genlight

gl2geno(gnl_filt, outfile = "geno", outpath = getwd(), verbose = NULL) # Produces a geno/ lfmm objects in the working
directory

# Read the geno file
library(LEA)
geno_filt <- read.geno("geno.geno")

colnames(geno_filt) <- colnames (gendf_filt)
rownames(geno_filt) <- rownames(gendf_filt)
dim(geno_filt) #324 4308

## [1] 324 4308

## Number of missing data
sum(is.na(gendf_filt)) #0

# Load Environmental dataset
# Loading extracted environmental values and Q-matrix based on sNMF
GEA_vars = read.csv("metenv_cluster.csv", row.names = 1)
GEA_facts = GEA_vars[, c(2,3, 7:17)]
head(GEA_facts)

##      lat lon PDrM_14 PSe_15 PCoQ_19 nitrogen silt clay
## GPE031260 26.20 88.56 3 108.97316 25 138.3811 392.4581 255.7799
## GPE031280 26.33 88.55 3 110.10744 25 144.2561 380.3331 248.7799
##      ocs P1 P2 P3 P4
## GPE031260 39.02538 0.2000780 0.5865110 0.213311000 9.99910e-05
## GPE031280 40.40038 0.0822464 0.5114870 0.406167000 9.99911e-05

# Make sure the genomic and environmental datasets are in the same order before further analysis
identical(row.names(GEA_facts), row.names(gendf_filt)) #True

```

4.2.2. Redundancy analysis (RDA)

Redundancy analysis (RDA) is a constrained ordination method used widely but particularly in landscape genomics analysis, models a linear relationship among environment factors and genomic variation to identifying allele frequencies associating with the multivariate environment. Its advantage is the ability to allow inclusion of unobserved variables such population structure to account for confounding factors when inferring genotype–environment associations on the landscape. This allows RDA to accommodate the genomic and environmental complexity found in nature making it a powerful tool in landscape genomics studies.

```

library(vegan) # For rda function

prda = rda(gendf_filt ~ PDrM_14 + PSe_15 + PCoQ_19 + nitrogen + silt + clay + ocs + Condition (P1 + P2 + P3 + P4 + lon +
lat), GEA_facts )

summary(prda)

# Quality
RsquareAdj(prda)

```

```

# Check our RDA model for significance using formal tests
signif.full = anova.cca(prda, permutations = 1000)
signif.full

#      Df Variance   F Pr(>F)
#Model   7  76.3 2.2546 0.01199 *
#Residual 310 1498.8
#Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
#Check our variable significance
signif.terms = anova.cca(prda, by="terms", permutations = 1000)
signif.terms
#      Df Variance   F Pr(>F)
#PDrM_14  1   9.46 1.9607 0.023976 *
#PSe_15   1   9.66 2.0028 0.053946 .
#PCoQ_19  1   9.25 1.9168 0.020979 *
#nitrogen  1   6.92 1.4346 0.068931 .
#silt     1  28.52 5.9116 0.000999 ***
#clay     1   7.38 1.5292 0.094905 .
#ocs      1   7.26 1.5050 0.075924 .

# Check significant axis
axis_sig = anova.cca(prda, by="axis", permutations = 1000)
axis_sig
#      Df Variance   F Pr(>F)
#RDA1     1  31.41 6.4970 0.04895 *
#RDA2     1  10.44 2.1597 0.29570
#RDA3     1  10.00 2.0692 0.22777
#RDA4     1   7.95 1.6452 0.27273
#RDA5     1   6.12 1.2655 0.37962
#RDA6     1   5.75 1.1885 0.31069
#RDA7     1   4.63 0.9573 0.26873

summary(eigenvals(prda, model="constrained"))

## Importance of components:
##              RDA1  RDA2  RDA3  RDA4  RDA5  RDA6  RDA7
## Eigenvalue      33.5557 10.8525 9.2790 7.9385 6.52930 6.0325 4.25647
## Proportion Explained 0.4278 0.1383 0.1183 0.1012 0.08324 0.0769 0.05426
## Cumulative Proportion 0.4278 0.5661 0.6844 0.7856 0.86884 0.9457 1.00000

## We chose the first 3 axes, which explained 67.96% of the variation
# Plotting the RDA
# Plot samples and the environmental predictors
levels(GEA_vars$Region) = c("C. Bgd", "C. Ind", "E. Ind", "N. Bgd", "NE. Ind", "S. Bgd", "S. Ind") # We plot using the assigned
populations
eco = as.factor (GEA_vars$Region)
bg = RColorBrewer::brewer.pal(7, "Paired")

# Axes 1 & 2
plot(prda, type="n", scaling=2, xlim=c(-5,5), ylim=c(-6,5), xlab='RDA1 (42.78%)', ylab='RDA2 (13.83%)', main="S. melongena,
pRDA, axes 1_2")
# The species
points(prda, display="sites", pch=21, cex=1.6, col="gray32", scaling=2, bg=bg[eco])
# The predictors

```

```

text(prda, scaling=2, display="bp", col="#191970", cex=1.2)
col="gray32", pch=21, cex=1.2, pt.bg=bg)
legend("bottomright", legend=levels(eco), bty="n",

# Axes 1 & 3
plot(prda, type="n", scaling=1, xlim=c(-5,5), ylim=c(-6,6), choices=c(1,3),xlab= 'RDA1 (42.78%)', ylab= 'RDA3 (11.83%)', main=
"S. melongena, pRDA, axes 1_3")
points(prda, display="sites", pch=21, cex=1.6, col="gray32", scaling=2, bg=bg[eco], choices=c(1,3))
text(prda, scaling=2, display="bp", col="#191970", cex=1.2, choices=c(1,3))
legend("topright", legend=levels(eco), bty="n", col="gray32", pch=21, cex=1.2, pt.bg=bg)

```

4.2.3. RDA outlier identification

In this manual we rely on the loading on the ordination space to identify our outliers (Capblancq et al., 2018). Here, we are looking at the loadings exceeding ± 3 standard deviations from the mean of each distribution. The ± 3 standard deviations can be changed depending on the level of stringency you would like to apply to your study. In the following example, we will derive the SNP loadings from the first three constrained RDA axes, explaining most of the variation. You can also choose your loadings just from the significant axes. In our case, only Axis 1 showed was significant.

```
## Finds SNPs outliers based on loadings
```

```

load.rda <- summary(prda)$species[,1:3] # Load the first 3 most informative axes (65.0%)
hist(load.rda[,1], main="Loadings on RDA1")
abline(v = c(mean(load.rda[,1])-3*sd(load.rda[,1]),
mean(load.rda[,1])+3*sd(load.rda[,1])))

```



```

hist(load.rda[,2], main="Loadings on RDA2")
abline(v = c(mean(load.rda[,1])-3*sd(load.rda[,1]),
mean(load.rda[,1])+3*sd(load.rda[,1])))

```



```
hist(load.rda[,3], main="Loadings on RDA3")
abline(v = c(mean(load.rda[,1])-3*sd(load.rda[,1]),
             mean(load.rda[,1])+3*sd(load.rda[,1])))
```



```
# The function for outliers here (Credits to Forester et al., 2018), where x is the vector of loadings and z is the standard
# deviation cut-off
outliers <- function(x,z){
  lims <- mean(x) + c(-1, 1) * z * sd(x) ## Find loadings +/- z SD from mean loading
  x[x < lims[1] | x > lims[2]]      # Locus names in these tails
}
# Apply the function to the first three constrained axes
cand1 <- outliers(load.rda[,1], 3) ## 59 SNps
```

```
cand2 <- outliers(load.rda[,2], 3) ## 21 SNPs
cand3 <- outliers(load.rda[,3], 3) ## 35 SNPs
```

The numbers align well with what is expected when we look at the histograms of the 3 axes. Considering the positions of the ablines, we expected the highest numbers on axis 1 and the lowest on axis 2. A conservative SD ± 3 has been applied. Sometimes, a more liberal value of 2.5 can be used. Try both to see the outcome

```
# To see the names of the candidates
prda_cand <- c(names(cand1), names(cand2), names(cand3))
prda_cand #115 candidates

## [1] "S1_4910091" "S1_12528934" "S1_12537459" "S1_19640524"
## [113] "S10_1071558" "S10_15505971" "S12_73974138"
```

```
# Let's find out if any of the outlier SNPs are duplicated on our three axes
length(prda_cand[duplicated(prda_cand)]) # 10 SNPs are duplicates
```

```
# Remove duplicates
prda_cand <- prda_cand[!duplicated(prda_cand)] # 105 unique candidates
```

4.2.4. Choice of outlier method

The two outlier selection methods produce varied numbers of outliers. This is the case because of the different working backgrounds of the methods. Remember, though, that a significant level of choosing the outliers in the first method is 0.05. In contrast, a two-tailed p-value equal to or lower than 0.0027 (± 3) is applied in the second case. In our case, the selected number of outliers do not vary significantly (104 and 115 SNPs).

```
# Definition of the outlier-environments association based on the highest correlation between each candidate SNP and the
environmental variables used in the study
```

```
# Make one data frame with the axis, SNP name, loading, and correlation with each predictor
```

```
cand1 <- cbind.data.frame(rep(1,times=length(cand1)), names(cand1), unname(cand1))
cand2 <- cbind.data.frame(rep(2,times=length(cand2)), names(cand2), unname(cand2))
cand3 <- cbind.data.frame(rep(3,times=length(cand3)), names(cand3), unname(cand3))
colnames(cand1) <- colnames(cand2) <- colnames(cand3) <- c("axis", "snp", "loading")
```

```
RDAcand <- rbind(cand1, cand2, cand3)
RDAcand$snp <- as.character(RDAcand$snp)
```

```
# Add in the correlations of each candidate SNP with the eight environmental predictors
```

```
foo <- matrix(nrow=(cand), ncol=7) # 7 columns for 7 predictors
colnames(foo) <- c("PDrM_14", "PSe_15", "PCoQ_19", "nitrogen", "silt", "clay", "ocs")
```

```
for (i in 1:length(RDAcand$snp)) {
  nam <- RDAcand[i,2]
  snp.gen <- gendf_filt[,nam]
  foo[i,] <- apply(GEA_facts[,c(3:9)], 2, function(x) cor(x, snp.gen))
}
```

```
RDAcand <- cbind.data.frame(RDAcand, foo)
head(RDAcand) #Check the dataframe
```

```
# Next, we find out which of the environmental predictors each candidate SNP is most strongly correlated with
```

```

for (i in 1:length(RDAcand$snp)) {
  bar <- RDAcand[i,]
  RDAcand[i,11] <- names(which.max(abs(bar[4:10]))) # gives the variable
  RDAcand[i,12] <- max(abs(bar[4:10])) # gives the correlation
}

colnames(RDAcand)[11] <- "predictor"
colnames(RDAcand)[12] <- "correlation"

view(RDAcand) # View the data frame

# Store the dataframe in the directory
write.csv(RDAcand, 'candVsVars_corr.csv', row.names = FALSE)

# We can quickly view a table of the variables and the number of SNPs associated with each of the variables
table(RDAcand$predictor)

## clay nitrogen ocs PCoQ_19 PDrM_14 PSe_15 silt
## 20 2 9 11 8 21 44

# Visualize candidate SNPs in the ordination space

sel <- RDAcand$snp
env <- RDAcand$predictor

env[env=="PDrM_14"] = '#fb9a99'
env[env=="PSe_15"] = '#1f78b4'
env[env=="PCoQ_19"] = '#FF8000'
env[env=="nitrogen"] = '#a0522d'
env[env=="silt"] = '#e31a1c'
env[env=="clay"] = '#a6cee3'
env[env=="ocs"] = '#33a02c'

# Color by predictor
col.pred <- rownames(prda$CCA$v) # Pull the SNP names

for (i in 1:length(sel)) { # Color code candidate SNPs
  foo <- match(sel[i],col.pred)
  col.pred[foo] <- env[i]
}

col.pred[grep('_',col.pred)] <- '#f1eef6' # Non-candidate SNPs
empty <- col.pred
empty[grep("#f1eef6",empty)] <- rgb(0,1,0, alpha=0) # Transparent
empty.outline <- ifelse(empty=="#00FF0000", "#00FF0000", "gray32")
bg <- c('#fb9a99', '#1f78b4', '#FF8000', '#a0522d', '#e31a1c', '#a6cee3', '#33a02c')

# Plot the SNPs
# Axes 1 & 2
plot(prda, type="n", scaling=3, xlim=c(-2,2), ylim=c(-2,2), xlab= 'RDA1 (42.78%)', ylab= 'RDA2 (13.83%)', main= "S.
melongena, pRDA, axes 1_2")
points(prda, display="species", pch=19, cex=1.5, col="gray", bg=col.pred, scaling=1)
points(prda, display="species", pch=21, cex=1.5, col=empty.outline, bg=empty, scaling=1)
text(prda, scaling=3, display="bp", col="#191970", cex=1.2)
legend("topright", legend=c("PDrM_14", "PSe_15", "PCoQ_19", "nitrogen", "silt", "clay", "ocs"), bty="n", col="gray",
pch=21, cex=1.2, pt.bg=bg)

```

S. melongena, pRDA, axes 1_2

Axes 1 & 3

```
plot(prda, type="n", scaling=3, xlim=c(-2,2), ylim=c(-2,3), xlab='RDA1 (42.78%)', ylab='RDA3 (11.83%)', main="S. melongena, pRDA, axes 1_3")
```

```
points(prda, display="species", pch=19, cex=1.5, col="gray", bg=col.pred, scaling=1, choices=c(1,3))
```

```
points(prda, display="species", pch=21, cex=1.5, col=empty.outline, bg=empty, scaling=1, choices=c(1,3))
```

```
text(prda, scaling=3, display="bp", col="#191970", cex=1.2, choices=c(1,3))
```

```
legend("topright", legend=c("PDrM_14", "PSe_15", "PCoQ_19", "nitrogen", "silt", "clay", "ocs"), bty="n", col="gray", pch=21, cex=1.2, pt.bg=bg)
```

S. melongena, pRDA, axes 1_3

NOTE: Most outlier SNPs detected on the first three significant axes are highly correlated to the soil silt content and annual precipitation seasonality (shown in red and dark-blue dots in the figures).

4.2.5. Latent factor mixed models (LFMM)

Latent factor mixed models is an equally efficient methods for inferring gene-environment correlations while simultaneously detect inferring population structure in the background. This makes it efficiently estimate the effects due to population history and isolation-by-distance patterns when computing gene-environment correlations, and decrease the number of false-positive associations in genome scans (Frichot et al., 2015).

```
# Now, let's upload the QC-ed environmental matrix we produced and stored after combining it with the population structure information in Section A
```

```
X = read.csv("metenv_cluster.csv", row.names = 1)
```

```
# Selecting the environmental variables only
```

```
X1 = X[, c(7:13)]
```

```
head(X1)
```

```
##      PDrM_14 PSe_15 PCoQ_19 nitrogen silt clay ocs
## GPE031260   3 108.97316   25 138.3811 392.4581 255.7799 39.02538
## GPE031280   3 110.10744   25 144.2561 380.3331 248.7799 40.40038
```

```
# The lfmm format is required for LFMM analysis. See the generation of the lfmm in Section 2.
```

```
# Loading the genotype matrix (molecular matrix: independent variables)
```

```
Y = read.lfmm("./geno.lfmm")
```

```
Y[1:2, 1:2]
```

```
##      V1 V2 V3 V4 V5 V6 V7 V8 V9 V10
## [1,] 2 2 2 2 1 1 2 2 2 2
## [2,] 1 1 2 2 1 0 1 1 2 2
```

```
# After loading all the necessary data, we can now begin the LFMM analysis
```

```
library(lfmm)
```

```
# The K argument specifies how many latent factors we need to describe population structure
```

```
# LFMM requires estimating the number of populations in the data (K)
```

```
# In our case, we will use the K=4 value obtained from the STRUCTURE and sNMF methods
```

```
# Alternatively, as a quick check in case no parallel population structure analysis has been done to determine K, PCA on the genomic data can be used, noting that there are many different approaches for determining K from genetic data (more in the population structure analysis section). It is also reasonable to run LFMM with different values of K, if there is uncertainty on the K value
```

```
gen.pca_lfmm = vegan::rda(Y, scale = TRUE)
```

```
screplot(gen.pca_lfmm, main = "Screeplot of Genetic Data with Broken Stick", bstick=TRUE, type="barplot")
```

Screeplot of Genetic Data with Broken Stick

A broken stick criterion can determine K for the PCA on genomic data. The broken stick-stopping rule states that principal components should be retained if observed eigenvalues exceed corresponding random broken stick components. For example, in the PCA scree plot below with a broken stick criterion, PC1 to PC8 explain more than the random broken stick components, while those from PC9 onwards do not. In this case, we would set K = 8, but to keep with the K value estimates using STRUCTURE and sNMF, we will use K = 4

```
lfmm_analysis <- lfmm_ridge(Y = Y, X = X1, K = 4)
```

Now we can compute the p-values for all the SNP environment associations performed and calibrate them by a genomic inflation factor ('calibrate = "gif"')

```
lfmm_pvalues <- lfmm_test(Y = gendf_filt, X = X1, lfmm = lfmm_analysis, calibrate = "gif")
```

To check the components

```
names(lfmm_pvalues)
```

```
## [1] "B"          "epsilon.sigma2" "B.sigma2"
```

```
## [4] "score"     "pvalue"      "gif"
```

```
## [7] "calibrated.score2" "calibrated.pvalue"
```

Check the GIFs

```
lfmm_pvalues$gif
```

```
## PDrM_14 PSe_15 PCoQ_19 nitrogen silt clay ocs
```

```
## 1.433351 2.033219 1.968846 1.133921 1.848330 1.897518 1.533963
```

Our GIFs look well-calibrated. An appropriately calibrated set of tests will have a GIF of around 1. Elevated GIFs may indicate that the results may be overly liberal in identifying candidate SNPs. The test may be too conservative if the GIF is less than 1

#NOTE: Changing the value of K influences the GIF, so additional tests using the "best" value of K +/- 1 may be needed in some cases. See Francois et al. (2016) for more details

#Check if the distribution of the p-value agrees with the FDR assumption

```
hist(lfmm_pvalues$pvalue[,1], xlab = "unadjusted P-values", main = "Distribution of Unadjusted P-values of LFMM (K = 4)")
```

Distribution of Unadjusted P-values of LFMM (K = 4)


```
hist(lfmm_pvalues$calibrated.pvalue[,1], xlab = "GIF-adjusted P-values", main = "Distribution of Adjusted P-values of LFMM (K = 4)")
```

Distribution of Adjusted P-values of LFMM (K = 4)


```
# Saving calibrated p-values  
pvalues_lfmm <- lfmm_pvalues$calibrated.pvalue # Pull out and store the pvalues  
  
# Adding SNP IDs to 'lfmm_pvalues' for sake of clarity  
rownames(pvalues_lfmm) = colnames(read.csv("gendf_filt.csv", row.names = 1))
```

```

# You may want to store the p-values data frame for later reference
write.csv(pvalues_lfmm, "lfmm_pvalues.csv")

# Visualizing the difference between the expected and observed p-value distributions
# A preliminary inspection of the occurrence of significant associations through Quantile-Quantile plots

par(mfrow = c(3,3), mar = c(3.5,4,3,0.5), mgp = c(2.5,0.8,0))
for (i in 1:ncol(pvalues_lfmm)) {
  qqplot(rexp(length(pvalues_lfmm[,i]), rate=log(10)), -log10(pvalues_lfmm[,i]),
    xlab="Expected quantile", ylab=expression(-log[10] ~ p-values),
    pch=19, cex=0.4, main=colnames(pvalues_lfmm)[i])
  abline(0, 1)
}

```



```

# Visualize the histograms of p-values for each environmental variable
par(mfrow = c(3,3), mar = c(3.5,3.5,3,0.5), mgp = c(2.5,0.8,0))

for (i in 1:ncol(pvalues_lfmm)) {
  hist(pvalues_lfmm[, i], breaks=20, xlab="p-values", xlim=c(0, 1),
    main=colnames(pvalues_lfmm)[i], col="darkgray", border="darkgray")
}

```


Calculate the q-value for each GEA test, respectively

```
library(qvalue)
```

```
lfmm_qvalues <- apply(pvalues_lfmm,2, function(x){qvalue(x)$qvalues})
```

Store the q_values

```
write.csv(lfmm_qvalues, "lfmm_qvalues.csv")
```

Number of significant SNPs for all environmental variables. The threshold applied here is more stringent at a 0.01 confidence level

```
lfmm_qv = as.data.frame(lfmm_qvalues)
```

To look at the total number of lfmm outliers. There are 171 significant SNPs in total for all environmental variables

```
length(which(lfmm_qv < 0.01))
```

```
## [1] 171
```

We can have all the detected SNPs for each environmental variable

```
PDrM_14snps = row.names(lfmm_qv)[which(lfmm_qv$PDrM_14 < 0.01)] #3
```

```
PSe_15snps = row.names(lfmm_qv)[which(lfmm_qv$PSe_15 < 0.01)] #3
```

```
PCoQ_19snps = row.names(lfmm_qv)[which(lfmm_qv$PCoQ_19 < 0.01)] #63
```

```
nitro_snps = row.names(lfmm_qv)[which(lfmm_qv$nitrogen < 0.01)] #12
```

```
silt_snps = row.names(lfmm_qv)[which(lfmm_qv$silt < 0.01)] #87
```

```
clay_snps = row.names(lfmm_qv)[which(lfmm_qv$clay < 0.01)] #0
```

```
ocs_snps = row.names(lfmm_qv)[which(lfmm_qv$ocs < 0.01)] #3
```

```

# Combine all the SNPs associated with each environmental variable

lfmm_outliers = c(PDrM_14snps, PSe_15snps, PCoQ_19snps, nitro_snps, silt_snps, clay_snps, ocs_snps)

# We make the dataframe for the environmental variables and the names of the SNPs associated with each of the
variables for storage

lfmmelist = tibble::lst(PDrM_14snps, PSe_15snps, PCoQ_19snps, nitro_snps, silt_snps, clay_snps, ocs_snps)
lfmmoutlier_df = data.frame(lapply(lfmmelist, `length<-`, max(lengths(lfmmelist))))
write.csv(lfmmoutlier_df, "lfmmoutlier_df.csv", row.names = FALSE)

```

NOTE: Landscape genomic studies should carefully consider the issue of false positives. You should note that applying stricter thresholds to address this issue might result in lower power to detect true positives. It will inflate the rate of false negatives. One additional way is to combine approaches to compare outcomes. This is a best practice in exploratory studies (see Forester et al., 2018).

4.3. Differentiation outlier methods

For this manual, we apply PCAdapt as our outlier differentiation method. Several other alternatives can be used, for example, BAYESCAN (Foll and Gaggiotti 2008), FDIST and derivatives (Beaumont and Balding 2004; Beaumont and Nichols 1996), FLK (Bonhomme et al., 2010), or ARLEQUIN (Excoffier and Lischer, 2010).

4.3.1. PCAdapt

PCAdapt outlier differentiation method uses a PCA-based approach to simultaneously infer population structure and identify outlier loci related to this structure. In contrast to the previous GEA methods, it does not return associations between obtained SNPs and the selected environmental factors (Luu et al., 2016). With this different approach, we expected to capture other candidate SNPs not yet captured by the GEA methods above.

Start of Script 4.3.1.

```

library(pcadapt)
lfmm = read.lfmm("geno.lfmm")
pcad = read.pcadapt(t(lfmm))
# Define our population
Pop = GEA_vars$Region
K1 = 12

x <- pcadapt(pcad, K = K1)
plot(x, option = "screplot") # 3 groups seems to be the correct value considering Cattell's rule (leveling off elbow)

```

Scree Plot - K = 12


```
K2 <- 3
```

```
x <- pccadapt(pccad, K = K2)
```

```
plot(x, option = "scores", pop = Pop) # How populations are shared among the 7 groups
```

Projection onto PC1 and PC2


```
summary(x) # Numerical quantities obtained after performing a PCA
```

```
plot(x, option = "screplot")
```

Scree Plot - K = 3


```
plot(x, option = "qqplot")
```

Q-Q plot


```
# Histograms of the test statistic and the p-value  
# A histogram of p-values confirms that most p-values follow a uniform distribution  
# The excess of small p-values indicates the presence of outliers
```

```
hist(x$pvalues, xlab = "p-values", main = NULL, breaks = 50, col = "orange")
```


To shows the statistical distribution of the outliers

```
plot(x, option = "stat.distribution")
```


4.3.2. Choosing the cutoff for the outlier detection

An alpha (α) is chosen as the cutoff for the outlier detection. For a given α (a real-valued number between 0 and 1), SNPs with q-values less than α will be considered outliers with an expected false discovery rate bounded by α . The q-value refers to the adjusted p-value for a given SNP and indicates the probability that a particular SNP association with a trait is a false positive, taking into account the multiple comparisons performed in a genome association study. SNPs with low q-value (for example, below α) have significant association with an environmental variable with a low likelihood of being a false positive. The false discovery rate is defined as the percentage of false discoveries among the list of candidate SNPs. Here is an example of how to provide a list of candidate SNPs for an expected false discovery rate lower than 5%.

Adjusting the p-value can also be achieved using several methods, such as Bonferroni and Benjamini-Hochberg. The methods vary in conservativeness, depending on the level of stringency a study requires.

Start of Script 4.3.2.

```
# 1. q-values  
library(qvalue) # Transforms p-values into q-values
```

```
qval <- qvalue(x$pvalues)$qvalues  
alpha <- 0.05  
qval_outliers <- which(qval < alpha)  
length(qval_outliers)#131
```

```
## [1] 131
```

```
# 2. Benjamini-Hochberg Procedure  
padj <- p.adjust(x$pvalues,method="BH")  
alpha <- 0.05  
BH_outliers <- which(padj < alpha)  
length(BH_outliers)#131
```

```
## [1] 131
```

```
# 3. Bonferroni correction  
padj <- p.adjust(x$pvalues,method="bonferroni")  
alpha <- 0.05  
BF_outliers <- which(padj < alpha)  
length(BF_outliers) #80
```

```
## [1] 80
```

```
#We further extract the outlier SNP names from the SNP dataframe.
```

```
outlier_names = subset(gendf_filt, TRUE, c(BF_outliers))  
outlier_names
```

```
outliers_pcadapt = colnames (outlier_names)  
outliers_pcadapt
```

```
# Store the outlier names
```

```
write.csv(outliers_pcadapt, "pcadapt_outliers", row.names = F)
```

4.4. Shared signatures of divergent selection among pRDA, LFMM, and PCAdapt

Using a Venn diagram, we can see overlapping SNPs (numbers) among the GEA and outlier differentiation methods. This is important so as to retrieve only SNP that are commonly detected by the different methods. This step helps to further narrow down to only the loci that are likely to be true positives.

```
outliers = c(prda_cand, lfmm_outliers,outliers_pcadapt) # All the SNP candidates  
outliers # 356
```

```
outl_list = tibble::lst(prda_cand, lfmm_outliers ,outliers_pcadapt)  
outl_df = data.frame(lapply(outl_list, 'length<-`', max(lengths(outl_list))))  
write.csv(outl_df, "outliers_df.csv", row.names = FALSE)
```

```
# To retain only the unique candidates (348 SNP candidates)
```

```

outl_cand = unique(c(prda_cand, lfmm_outliers,outliers_pcadapt)) #348 unique SNP candidates

# Subset the genomic data dataframe by the outliers
Outgen_df <- gendf_filt[, which((names(gendf_filt) %in% outliers)==TRUE)]
dim(Outgen_df)

## [1] 324 348

# Store in the directory for later downstream analysis
write.csv(Outgen_df, "outgen_df.csv", row.names = TRUE)

# Intersecting the outliers
lfmm_outliers # lfmm candidates
prda_cand # pRDA candidates
outliers_pcadapt # PCAdapt candidates

commom_snps = Reduce(intersect, list(lfmm_outliers, prda_cand, outliers_pcadapt)) # 0 SNPs overlap among all the 3
methods

# We can plot a ven diagram to represent the interaction
library("VennDiagram")
myCol <- c('#1f78b4','#FF8000','#33a02c')
venn.diagram(
  x = list(lfmm_outliers, # 184
    prda_cand, # 97
    outliers_pcadapt), # 80
  category.names = c("LFMM", "pRDA", "PCAdapt"),
  filename = 'Outliers_venndiag.png',
  output=TRUE,

# Output features
  imagetype="png",
  height = 1000,
  width = 1000,
  resolution = 600,
  compression = "lzw",
# Circles
  lwd = 0.2,
  lty = 'dashed',
  fill = myCol,
# Numbers
  cex = .3,
  fontface = "bold",
  fontfamily = "sans",
# Set names
  cat.cex = 0.3,
  cat.fontface = "bold",
  cat.default.pos = "outer",
  cat.fontfamily = "sans")

```


4.5. Candidate gene annotation using a reference genome

Once the candidate NSPs have been identified, the next step is identifying the candidate genes where the SNPs are located. For this step, you require reference data containing information about the genomic coordinates of genomic features, such as the gene annotation files. For gene annotation files, you need the GFF file. Reference data files include:

- General biological databases (e.g., Ensembl, NCBI).
- Organism-specific biological databases (e.g., the Sol Genomics Network data FTP database for the eggplant genome consortium).

For the annotation in this manual, candidate SNP coordinates on candidate genes were identified using the Sol Genomics Network data FTP database for the eggplant genome consortium Version 4.1 (Barchi et al., 2021) (https://solgenomics.net/organism/Solanum_melongena/genome) as the reference genome for generating genomic data. The candidate gene search and gene ontology terms were assigned using the Arabidopsis information resource (tair) (<https://www.arabidopsis.org/>) and Uniprot (<https://www.uniprot.org/>) databases. Genes and their functions were characterized, particularly those associated with abiotic stress and relevant to eggplant adaptation (Omondi et al., 2025).

Ensembl (<http://useast.ensembl.org/index.html>) and Ensembl Plants (<http://plants.ensembl.org/index.html>) provide websites acting as a single point of access to annotated genomes for both animals and plants. All organisms except viruses can be accessed on Ensembl Genomes (<http://ensemblgenomes.org/>). Apart from accessing the databases through the browser, it is possible to obtain data directly into R through different functions in the biomaRt package. The functions are tailored to work specifically with the BioMart instances provided by Ensembl Genomes. For more specific detailed functionality, refer to the biomaRt vignette (https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/vignettes/biomaRt/inst/doc/accessing_ensembl.html).

5. Modeling genomic dynamics at landscape level and under climate change

Aims

- To estimate the adaptive landscape of the studied populations.
- To estimate the maladaptation across the landscape of the studied populations.

5.1. Adaptive landscape

After identifying candidate adaptive markers and their corresponding environmental influencers using genome-environment association (GEA) analysis, the relationship between genotype and environment can be leveraged to predict an index of genetic composition on the landscape (Capblancq et al., 2021).

Steane et al. (2014) describe a precise procedure that uses the scores of the environmental variables along the RDA axes to calculate a genetic-based index of adaptation for each environmental pixel of the landscape. This index is estimated independently for each RDA axis of interest using the formula:

$$\text{Adaptive Index} = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i,$$

Where a is the climatic variable score (loading) along the RDA axis, b is the standardized value for this particular variable at the focal pixel, and i refers to one of the n different variables used in the RDA model (Supporting Information 1). The climatic variable scores used here are estimated based on how each predictor affects (magnitude and direction) adaptive genetic variation along the RDA axes. The adaptive index thus provides an estimate of adaptive genetic similarity or difference of all pixels on the landscape as a function of the values of the environmental predictors at that location (Capblancq et al., 2020). The adaptively enriched genetic space shows how the genetic markers correlate with the different bioclimatic variables and how the bioclimatic variables correlate.

Be reminded that any prediction procedure such as this relies on extrapolating correlative relationships and has potential pitfalls. Predicting any genetic-based adaptive index in unsampled areas could be strongly biased if the value or combination of the environmental predictors in those projected areas exceeds those used to train the model. Similarly, any projection could be inaccurate if the genetic-environment relationship is not well characterized, either because the scale of the analyses (e.g., size of the pixel) does not capture the complexity of the association or because the distribution of the identified genetic variation is not optimal across the current and future environmental landscape (e.g., due to recent demographic history, barriers to gene flow, genetic drift in small populations, fluctuating trait heritability, varying selection pressures, or genetic architecture). It is critical to avoid overinterpreting adaptive index projections, especially when validation data are unavailable.

Start of Script 5.1.1.

```
# We will derive an RDA-based adaptive index by following the procedure explained in (Capblancq et al., 2020  
https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13722)
```

```
# Prepare the shape files of the region of Study  
library(sf)
```

```
bng = st_read("D:/DATA/EggplantSPET/LSG_manual/Bgd Shp/BGD_adm0.shp")  
ind = st_read("D:/DATA/EggplantSPET/LSG_manual/India shp/IND_adm0.shp")  
indbng = rbind(bng, ind) # Combine the India and Bangladesh shape files  
plot(indbng$geometry) # Checking the shape file
```


We load the environmental data stored in the working directory in Section 2.1.

```
# Loading extracted environmental values, Qmatrix, and individual clusters based on sNMF
GEA_vars = read.csv("metenv_cluster.csv", row.names = 1)
head(GEA_vars)
```

```
Env = GEA_vars[, c(7:13)]
```

```
# Standardization of the environmental variables
Env_scl <- (scale(Env, center=TRUE, scale=TRUE))
Env_df = as.data.frame(Env_scl)
head(Env_scl)
```

```
##      PDrM_14 PSe_15 PCoQ_19 nitrogen silt clay
## GPE031260 -0.3193525 0.1973668 -0.1830975 -0.065371677 0.9318727 -2.108436
## GPE031280 -0.3193525 0.2753689 -0.1830975 0.002577541 0.7222096 -2.283617
##          ocs
## GPE031260 -0.3959960
## GPE031280 -0.2220487
```

To derive an adaptive landscape, we focus on the sole outliers resulting from Landscape Genomic Analysis. Therefore, we need to create a new genomic data set composed of the set of outliers only. We will only use the outliers detected by the GEA methods (LFMM and pRDA outliers) because they are associated with environmental variables. Otherwise, you may also include outliers obtained by outlier differentiation methods to see how different the results are. You can prepare this dataset by filtering it using Plink or TASSEL. A subset of the shared SNPs is the best choice to focus on.

```
# Outliers dataframe
Outgen_df = read.csv("outgen_df.csv", row.names = 1)
```

```
# View(Outgen_df)
```

2. Once the data set of candidate SNPs is created, the second step is to run the 'adaptively enriched' RDA, this time without conditioning for population structure

```
library(vegan)
```

```
RDA_outliers <- rda(Outgen_df ~ PDrM_14 + PSe_15 + PCoQ_19 + nitrogen + silt + clay + ocs, data = Env_df)
```

A look at the RDA biplot (adaptively enriched RDA space) to have an idea about the association between markers and the environment

```
plot(RDA_outliers, type="n", scaling=3, xlim=c(-1,1), ylim=c(-1,1), main = "Adaptively enriched RDA space")
```

```
points(RDA_outliers, display="species", pch=16, cex=1, col="orange", scaling=3)
```

```
text(RDA_outliers, scaling=3, display="bp", col="navyblue", cex=1)
```


Now, we need to identify the significant RDA axes to be used in the calculation of the adaptive index

```
signif.axis <- anova.cca(RDA_outliers, by = "axis", parallel = getOption("mc.cores"), permutations = 5000) # Number of permutations affect the results
```

3. Now, we can calculate the adaptive index across the landscape; a prediction of adaptive similarity across the landscape based on the relative importance of the main environmental drivers of divergent selection in shaping adaptive variation

Raster stack of the environmental variables used

```
library(raster)
```

Load the environmental raster stack from the section on variables selection

```
ras1 = brick('Env_ras1.gri')
```

```
names(ras1)
```

```
## [1] "AMT_1" "MTWaQ_10" "MTCoQ_11" "AP_12" "PWeM_13" "PDrM_14"
## [7] "PSe_15" "PWeQ_16" "PDrQ_17" "PWaQ_18" "PCoQ_19" "MDiR_2"
## [13] "Iso_3" "TSe_4" "MTWaM_5" "MiTCoQ_6" "TAR_7" "MTWeQ_8"
## [19] "MTDrQ_9" "tmin" "tmax" "srad" "vapr" "wind"
## [25] "cec" "clay" "nitrogen" "ocd" "ocs" "pH"
## [31] "sand" "silt" "soc"
```

```
# Select the environmental raster stack for the selected environmental variables
stack_env = ras1[[c("PDrM_14", "PSe_15", "PCoQ_19", "nitrogen", "silt", "clay", "ocs")]]
```

```
# As we are going to multiply the scores of the environmental variables by their standardized values, we need to retrieve the scaling coefficients of the standardized environmental matrix we used in RDA above
```

```
scale_Env <- attr(Env_scl, 'scaled:scale')
center_Env <- attr(Env_scl, 'scaled:center')
```

```
# Adaptive index calculation based on the 'adaptive_index()' function (Credits Capblancq and Forester 2021)
```

```
adaptive_landscape_current <- adaptive_index(
  RDA = RDA_outliers, # Adaptively enriched RDA
  K = 2, # Number of significant RDA axes
  env_pres = stack_env, # The rasters including current climate and soil
  range = indbng,
  method = "loadings", # Here we specify to use the loadings of the env. variables on the RDA axes in the calculation of the adaptive index
  scale_env = scale_Env, # Scaling coefficients
  center_env = center_Env)
```

```
# Plot the adaptive landscape based on the loading from RDA1
```

```
plot(adaptive_landscape_current$RDA1)
```

```
# Plot the adaptive landscape based on the loading from RDA2
```

```
plot(adaptive_landscape_current$RDA2)
```


The adaptive index thus provides an estimate of the adaptive genetic similarity or difference of all pixels on the landscape as a function of the values of the environmental predictors at that location. When projected on a map, it allows for visualization of the different adaptive gradients across a species range.

```
# Vectorization of the climatic rasters for ggplot following Capblancq and Forester 2021. (https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13722)
```

```
RDA_proj <- list(adaptive_landscape_current$RDA1, adaptive_landscape_current$RDA2)
```

```

RDA_proj <- lapply(RDA_proj, function(x) rasterToPoints(x))
for(i in 1:length(RDA_proj)){
  RDA_proj[[i]][,3] <- (RDA_proj[[i]][,3]-min(RDA_proj[[i]][,3]))/(max(RDA_proj[[i]][,3])-min(RDA_proj[[i]][,3]))
}

# Adaptive genetic turnover projected across India and Bangladesh for RDA1 and RDA2 indexes
TAB_RDA <- as.data.frame(do.call(rbind, RDA_proj[1:2]))
colnames(TAB_RDA)[3] <- "value"
TAB_RDA$variable <- factor(c(rep("RDA1", nrow(RDA_proj[[1]])), rep("RDA2", nrow(RDA_proj[[2]]))), levels =
c("RDA1", "RDA2"))

# Plot the global adaptive genetic turnover
library(ggplot2)

ggplot(data = TAB_RDA) +
  geom_sf(data = indbng, fill=gray(.9), size=0) +
  geom_raster(aes(x = x, y = y, fill = cut(value, breaks=seq(0, 1, length.out=10), include.lowest = T))) +
  scale_fill_viridis_d(alpha = 0.8, direction = -1, option = "A", labels = c("Negative scores", "", "", "", "Intermediate
scores", "", "", "", "Positive scores")) +
  geom_sf(data = indbng, fill=NA, size=0.1) +
  coord_sf(xlim = c(68.1434, 97.36225), ylim = c(6.745551, 35.49541), expand = TRUE) +
  xlab("Longitude") + ylab("Latitude") +
  guides(fill=guide_legend(title="Adaptive index")) +
  facet_grid(~ variable) +
  theme_bw(base_size = 11, base_family = "Times") +
  theme(panel.grid = element_blank(), plot.background = element_blank(), panel.background = element_blank(), strip.text
= element_text(size=11))

```


End of Script 5.1.1.

5.2. Genomic offset

Assessing how climate change could disrupt local adaptation to climate can provide a new way of understanding population/individual risk and vulnerability to climate change. Several research studies now use genomic data at the population levels to assess the impact of changing climate on gene-environment interactions. These studies project the anticipated optimal genomic composition of populations onto future climatic scenarios after examining how the current adaptive genomic makeup corresponds to climate conditions. However, forecasting the potential decrease in fitness due to climate change is done assuming no immediate evolutionary changes, such as alterations in allele frequencies, recombination, migration, or mutation. Refer to Capblancq, Fitzpatrick, et al. (2020) for a detailed review of genomic offset prediction.

Start of Script 5.2.1.

```
# Shape file
# Prepare the shape files of the study region
library(sf)
library(raster)

bng = st_read("D:/DATA/EggplantSPET/LSG_manual/Bgd Shp/BGD_adm0.shp")
ind = st_read("D:/DATA/EggplantSPET/LSG_manual/India shp/IND_adm0.shp")
indbng = rbind(bng, ind) #combine the India and Bangladesh shape files

# Current climate data####
# To estimate the current, optimal adaptive landscape, we upload the raster tack for the current environmental data
ras1 = brick('Env_ras1.gri') # Environmental raster stack from the variable_selection.Rmd
names(ras1)

## [1] "AMT_1" "MTWaQ_10" "MTCoQ_11" "AP_12" "PWeM_13" "PDrM_14"
## [7] "PSe_15" "PWeQ_16" "PDrQ_17" "PWaQ_18" "PCoQ_19" "MDiR_2"
## [13] "Iso_3" "TSe_4" "MTWaM_5" "MiTCoQ_6" "TAR_7" "MTWeQ_8"
## [19] "MTDrQ_9" "tmin" "tmax" "srad" "vapr" "wind"
## [25] "cec" "clay" "nitrogen" "ocd" "ocs" "pH"
## [31] "sand" "silt" "soc"

stack_env = ras1[[c("PDrM_14", "PSe_15", "PCoQ_19", "nitrogen", "silt", "clay", "ocs")]]

# Future climate data####
library(geodata)
dir.create(path = "Future_data")
Fut_clim = cmip6_world(model = "BCC-CSM2-MR", ssp = 585, time = "2061-2080", var = "bioc", res = 2.5, path =
"Future_data/")
names(Fut_clim)

# Crop the future climate data to the extent of the study area
Fut_clim1 = crop(Fut_clim, indbng)

# Select the same climatic variables as those previously selected for in the historical climatic data
env_fut = Fut_clim1[[c(14,15,19)]]

# Note that this is a SpatRaster. Let's change it to a raster and combine it with the soil data rasters later
env_fut = as(env_fut, "Raster")
names(env_fut) = c("PDrM_14", "PSe_15", "PCoQ_19")

# Since we do not have the future soil data, we will combine the same soil variable in the previous section with the future
```

```

climate data to make the combined future environmental rasters for our genomic offset analysis.
sel_soils = ras1[[c("nitrogen", "silt", "clay", "ocs")]]
stack_fut = raster::stack (env_fut, sel_soils)

# Prepare the environmental data
# Loading extracted environmental values and Qmatrix based on sNMF
GEA_vars = read.csv("metenv_cluster.csv", row.names = 1)
#head(GEA_vars) #check the data

Env = GEA_vars[,c(7:13)] # Select only the environmental variables

# Standardization of the environmental variables
Env_scl <- (scale(Env, center=TRUE, scale=TRUE))
Env_df = as.data.frame(Env_scl)

# As we are going to multiply the scores of the environmental variables by their standardized values, we need to retrieve
the scaling coefficients of the standardized environmental matrix we used in RDA above
scale_Env <- attr(Env_scl, 'scaled:scale')
center_Env <- attr(Env_scl, 'scaled:center')

# We must focus on the sole outliers resulting from Landscape Genomic Analysis to derive an adaptive landscape.
Therefore, we need to create a new genomic data set composed of the set of outliers only. You can prepare this dataset
by filtering using Plink or TASSEL; it is ready to be analyzed. This data set is composed of both LFMM and pRDA outliers. A
subset of the shared SNPs would probably be the best choice to focus on, but we seem to have very few (just 6)

# Outliers dataframe previously saved in the directory as
# write.csv(Outgen_df, "outliers_df.csv", row.names = TRUE)

Outgen_df = read.csv("outgen_df.csv", row.names = 1)

# 2. Once the data set of candidate SNPs is created, the second step is to run the adaptively enriched RDA, this time
without conditioning for population structure
library(vegan)

RDA_outliers <- rda(Outgen_df ~ PDrM_14 + PSe_15 + PCoQ_19 + nitrogen + silt + clay + ocs , data = Env_df )
RDA_outliers

# We use the genomic_offset() function (in the libraries section above) to predict genomic offset based on an RDA
modelCredit to Capblancq and Forester 2021

genomic_offset_70 <- genomic_offset(
  RDA = RDA_outliers, # adaptively enriched RDA
  K = 2, # Number of significant axes in the RDA analysis
  env_pres = stack_env, # Rasterstack for current conditions (the used in the 'adaptive_index()' call)
  env_fut = stack_fut, # Rasterstack for future conditions (same variables included in 'env_pres')
  range = indbng, # Shapefile representing the study area (e.g., the species distribution); not necessary in this particular
case
  method = "loadings", # Here we specify to use the environmental variables loadings on the RDA axes in the calculation of
the adaptive index
  scale_env = scale_Env, # Scaling coefficients
  center_env = center_Env)

# Finally, let's plot the predicted genomic offset based on RDA1 and RDA2,
as well as the predicted global genomic offset
plot(genomic_offset_70$Proj_offset$RDA1, main="Genomic offset based on RDA1")

```

Genomic offset based on RDA1


```
plot(genomic_offset_70$Proj_offset$RDA2, main="Genomic offset based on RDA2")
```

Genomic offset based on RDA2


```
plot(genomic_offset_70$Proj_offset_global, main="Global genomic offset")
```

Global genomic offset


```
# Load the passport data
met1 = read.csv("metenv_cluster.csv") #store in the directory
coord = met1[,c(4,3)]

sp_crd1 <- SpatialPointsDataFrame(coords = coord, data = met1, proj4string = CRS("+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84
+ellps=WGS84 +towgs84=0,0,0"))
#plot(sp_crd1)

# Let's add the group information based on population structure
sp_crd1@data$cluster = as.numeric(met1$cluster)
head(sp_crd1@data) # To see what is inside the data

# and based on that, let's assign a symbol code to each individual
sp_crd1@data$symbol <- NA
sp_crd1@data$symbol[which(sp_crd1@data$cluster == 1)] <- 21
sp_crd1@data$symbol[which(sp_crd1@data$cluster == 2)] <- 22
sp_crd1@data$symbol[which(sp_crd1@data$cluster == 3)] <- 23
sp_crd1@data$symbol[which(sp_crd1@data$cluster == 4)] <- 2

# legend.col()
#Credit to:https://aurelienmadouasse.wordpress.com/2012/01/13/legend-for-a-continuous-color-scale-in-r/
legend.col <- function(col, lev){
  opar <- par
  n <- length(col)
  bx <- par("usr")
  box.cx <- c(bx[2] + (bx[2] - bx[1]) / 1000,
              bx[2] + (bx[2] - bx[1]) / 1000 + (bx[2] - bx[1]) / 50)
  box.cy <- c(bx[3], bx[3])
  box.sy <- (bx[4] - bx[3]) / n
  xx <- rep(box.cx, each = 2)
```

```

par(xpd = TRUE)
for(i in 1:n){
  yy <- c(box.cy[1] + (box.sy * (i - 1)),
    box.cy[1] + (box.sy * (i)),
    box.cy[1] + (box.sy * (i)),
    box.cy[1] + (box.sy * (i - 1)))
  polygon(xx, yy, col = col[i], border = col[i])
}
par(new = TRUE)
plot(0, 0, type = "n",
  ylim = c(min(lev), max(lev)),
  yaxt = "n", ylab = "", xaxt = "n", xlab = "",
  frame.plot = FALSE)
axis(side = 4, las = 2, tick = FALSE, line = .25)
par <- opar
}
set.seed(100)

```

As mentioned above, predicting any genetic-based adaptive/maladaptive indices in unsampled areas could be strongly biased. For this reason, it is best to focus the predictions on our sampling points, as shown in the following processes. You can also do this to predict the adaptive index above.

```

# We begin by first extracting the genomic offset values at sampling locations
genomic_offset_RDA1 <- raster::extract(genomic_offset_70$Proj_offset$RDA1, coord)
genomic_offset_RDA2 <- raster::extract(genomic_offset_70$Proj_offset$RDA2, coord)
genomic_offset_global <- raster::extract(genomic_offset_70$Proj_offset_global, coord)

```

```

# Then plot the individuals with a color scheme reflecting their genomic offset
par(mar=c(5, 5, 3, 3.5)) # margins for the plot
plot(indbng$geometry, ylim = c(6.78, 32.90), # range(coord[,2])+c(-2,2)
  xlab = "Longitude", ylab = "Latitude",
  cex.lab = 1.5, col="lightgray", main = "Genomic offset based on RDA1",
  cex.main = 1.5, font.main = 1)

```

At this point, we add individuals with symbols based on the population structure analysis and colors. You can also do this by using the assigned populations in your study

```

# Genomic offset based on RDA1
plot(sp_crd1, add = TRUE, cex = 2,
  pch = sp_crd1@data$symbol,
  bg = rev(heat.colors(100))[cut(genomic_offset_RDA1, 100, label = FALSE)])
# legend.col(col = rev(heat.colors(100)), lev = genomic_offset_RDA1)

```

```

# Add a legend
legend("topleft", pch = c(21,22,23, 24), legend = c("Cl.1", "Cl.2", "Cl.3", "Cl.4"),
  pt.bg = "black", pt.cex=1.1, cex = 1.1)

```

```

axis(1); axis(2)
dev.off()

```



```

# The same but for genomic offset based on RDA2
par(mar=c(5, 5, 3, 3.5)) # margins for the plot
plot(indbng$geometry, ylim = c(6.78, 32.90),

# range(coor[,2])+c(-2,2)
  xlab = "Longitude", ylab = "Latitude",
  cex.lab = 1.5, col="lightgray", main = "Genomic offset based on RDA2",
  cex.main = 1.5, font.main = 1)

# Genomic offset based on RDA2
plot(sp_crd1, add = TRUE, cex = 2,
  pch = sp_crd1@data$symbol,
  bg = rev(heat.colors(100))[cut(genomic_offset_RDA2, 100, label = FALSE)])
# legend.col(col = rev(heat.colors(100)), lev = genomic_offset_RDA2)

# Add a legend
legend("topleft", pch = c(21,22,23, 24), legend = c("Cl.1", "Cl.2","Cl.3","Cl.4"),
  pt.bg = "black", pt.cex=1.1, cex = 1.1)
axis(1); axis(2)
dev.off()

```



```

# ...and for the predicted global offset (accounting for both RD1 and RD2 simultaneously)
par(mar=c(5, 5, 3, 3.5)) # Margins for the plot
plot(indbng$geometry, ylim = c(6.78, 32.90),

# range(coor[,2])+c(-2,2)
  xlab = "Longitude", ylab = "Latitude",
  cex.lab = 1.5, col="lightgray", main = "Global genomic offset",
  cex.main = 1.5, font.main = 1)

# Based on the global genomic offset (RDA1 and RDA2 combined)
plot(sp_crd1, add = TRUE, cex = 2,
  pch = sp_crd1@data$symbol,
  bg = rev(heat.colors(100))[cut(genomic_offset_global, 100, label = FALSE)])
# legend.col(col = rev(heat.colors(100)), lev = genomic_offset_global)
# Add a legend
legend("topleft", pch = c(21,22,23, 24), legend = c("Cl.1", "Cl.2","Cl.3","Cl.4"),
  pt.bg = "black", pt.cex=1.1, cex = 1.1)
axis(1); axis(2)
dev.off()

```


End of Script 5.2.1.

NOTE: As can be observed from results from this illustration, populations especially in the southern and central parts of India that mostly belong to cluster one, are predicted to have a high genomic offset in the future, considering climatic changes. The germplasm in these populations should therefore be given a special focus for conservation, since they are likely to be less self-sustaining under future climatic scenarios. However, since genomic offset uses genomic and environmental data and does not include phenotypic traits, precaution is advised when using genomic offset predictions (Rellstab et al., 2021). For this reason, one could apply genomic offset in combination with other approaches such as ecological niche modeling for a comparability when assessing the future vulnerability of populations.

SECTION C. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

6. Discussion

6.1. The variety in landscape genomics tools

Since different authors present their work in unique styles and levels, this manual also presents other online resources and methods that users can explore. Some of these resources have also contributed to the development of this manual. Some resources include:

1. Courses on RDA with examples (https://pmassicotte.github.io/stats-denmark-2019/07_rda.html#/; https://popgen.nescent.org/2018-03-27_RDA_GEA.html; <http://www.randigriffin.com/2017/05/23/mosquito-community-ecology-in-vegan.html>)
2. Capblancq and Forester (2021) <https://github.com/Capblancq/RDA-landscape-genomics>
3. Chambers et al. (2023) <https://github.com/TheWangLab/algatr>
4. Tom Jenkins https://github.com/Tom-Jenkins/seascape_rda_tutorial
5. Landscape genomics courses (<https://www.physalia-courses.org/courses-workshops>)

An overview of methods and software available for environmental association analysis in landscape genomics has been reviewed (Rellstab et al., 2015b). Some of these are available as R packages. They including:

1. BayeEnv (Günther and Coop, 2013)
2. SGLMM (Guillot et al., 2014)
3. Bayescenv (de Villemereuil and Gaggiotti, 2015)
4. Baypass (Gautier, 2015)
5. algatr (Chambers et al., 2023)
6. PCAdapt (<https://bcm-uga.github.io/pcadapt/articles/pcadapt.html>)
7. OutFLANK (https://github.com/whitlock/OutFLANK_)

6.2. Challenges in landscape genomics

The main challenge in landscape genomics at present is the high rate of false positives when identifying candidate loci signaling local adaptation. Divergent phenotypes and genotypes are evidence of local adaptation, when the divergence is in tandem with the environmental gradient. False positives are produced because it is sometimes difficult to distinguish divergent selection from the neutral effects of genetic drift or historical effects of demography that are unrelated to environmental selective pressures that mimic patterns produced by local adaptation.

Fortunately, many methods in environmental association analysis can control for the neutral genetic structure to solve this problem. Another source of false positives is that it can be difficult to distinguish between correlated environmental selective pressures. More specifically, observed correlations with a specific environmental factor can be due to adaptation to covarying factors that were not included in the analyses or excluded in the process of factor reduction. In these cases, the association, not the locus, represents a false positive (Rellstab et al., 2015b). In other words, the detected locus might play a role in local adaptation but is linked to a different factor. Moreover, correlations among loci (i.e., linkage disequilibrium between an adaptive locus and other variants) can result in a spurious correlation signal at linked variants (hitchhiking, Strasburg et al., 2012). Several measures, such as checking for linkage disequilibrium in the genomic data and using complementary or new environmental data sources, can help mitigate the problem. Generally, methods applied in LSG also keep evolving to better control the problem of false positives.

Identifying candidate loci forms the basis for understanding the physiological basis of adaptation. However, we must acknowledge the challenges that come with this task. The functional validation of these loci in specific environmental conditions is still lacking in LSG studies. This is a resource-intensive undertaking. But, with the advancements in plant biotechnology, including genome editing, we are hopeful that the validation of specific variants will be more easily achieved. The challenge remains the polygenic nature of the trait of interest. Local adaptation may result from several subtle changes in allelic frequency that contribute to (unknown) phenotypic traits, as observed for the natural variation of plant metabolites (Rowe et al., 2008).

A limited number of candidate loci detection has been experienced in LSG studies (Omondi et al., 2024; Chang et al., 2022; Mdladla et al., 2018). This has been attributed to several reasons, one of them being small genomic data sets representing a portion of the genomes. Generating genomic data from whole genome sequencing of all individuals in a study would be ideal for LSG studies, enabling the association of millions of single-nucleotide polymorphisms with known functions and locations. This has so far been limited because of the costs involved for the large sample sizes used in LSG. Using genome complexity reduction methods representing a significant fraction of the genome is appropriate.

6.3. Future directions

So far, many LSG studies have revealed the environment's low explanatory power (Dauphin et al., 2023). Using complementary environmental data that maximally represents the complexity of the landscape characteristics and interactions will improve the situation. For instance, neglecting biotic factors has greatly undermined the potential of LSG in identifying adaptive variations. Even though biotic and abiotic may be correlated, they often operate on different spatial and temporal scales and affect different genomic features, thus providing distinct insights into how selective forces may act in natural populations (Descombes et al., 2020). Biotic interactions such as predation, disease, and symbiosis are projected to change with changes in the abiotic climate environment (Blois et al., 2013). These biotic interactions may weaken the accuracy of genomic predictions since they are not factored into the prediction. Additionally, anthropogenic activities keep contracting species' ranges in the environment.

The genomic scan for local adaptation is the most affordable step toward exploiting the positive results of divergent selection. However, little investment in non-model crops has been an impediment. This has changed in the recent past with a shift of focus on these adapted crops that are now seen to hold potential for food security. Cheaper technologies being developed have also seen a significant development of the genomic resources of these crops. Ample resources are still required to characterize populations in different environments phenotypically. Advances in high-throughput plant phenotyping facilities give hope for accelerating characterization in the future.

Uncovering the genetic basis of local adaptation will shed light on the evolutionary forces acting on biodiversity and the mechanisms underlying environmental adaptation and stress response. One of the main foci in the study of local adaptation is the identification of divergent selection pressures that lead to local adaptation. Although local adaptation is frequently linked to climate for most studies, there is ample evidence that local adaptation, especially in plants, can arise due to different environmental factors, including biotic and non-climatic abiotic factors (Brachi et al., 2015). Omondi et al. (2024) have also found numerous adaptive signals in eggplant populations localized in genes conferring associations and resistance to microbial pathogens. These inferences call for more local adaptation studies incorporating a wide selection of environmental data, including below-ground environments, to reflect the landscape's complex nature.

Local adaptation is mainly thought to be dominant in wild populations experiencing minimal human intervention and agricultural input. However, crop landraces are alternative readily available resources for exploitation in mining unique alleles for local adaptation. Due to their cultivation history, landraces have already been acclimated to thrive in conditions of low-input agriculture, marginal lands, or stressful

environments. Studies in the main crops above have also evidenced this fact. Many crop landraces are now conserved in the world's major genebanks. They are also available *in situ* as farmers' collections.

Landscape genomics approaches are moving beyond identifying candidate loci signaling local adaptation to provide insights on local fitness in a given environment by generating predictions of individual/population performance over space and time in landscapes. It is possible to predict the distribution of adaptive genetic variants along climate gradients using current climate conditions to yield a consistent estimate of allele frequencies at genetic sites associated with climate adaptation throughout a species' geographical range. This approach also extends predictions to geographical areas lacking individual or population genotypic data but with available climate information (Bay et al., 2018; Capblancq et al., 2020; Fitzpatrick and Keller, 2015; Steane et al., 2014). This information is helpful in conservation strategies, environmental restorations, genetic improvement programs, and crop field trials.

6.4. Conclusions

Landscape genomics is rapidly advancing with the ability to generate genomic datasets, even for non-model species. Enhanced environmental data, improved analysis methods, cost reduction, and ease of generating genomic data are expected to boost landscape genomic studies. These advancements will deepen our understanding of how specific genotypes adapt to their environments, both now and under future predicted conditions (Fitzpatrick and Keller 2015).

This manual provides insights into the fundamental steps and considerations for landscape genomic studies. We have selected a few commonly applied methods, though various techniques are available depending on the user's computational capacity and proficiency. Additionally, we present a collection of R scripts useful for achieving specific outcomes and creating simplified graphical displays of the results. We acknowledge that study scenarios differ, and the complexity can vary depending on the organism and landscapes involved. Applying LSG will significantly advance our understanding of biodiversity, informing effective genetic rescue and conservation strategies and crop development programs. Continued research will expand and refine these methods, broadening the range of taxa for comparison.

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World Vegetable Center

PO Box 42 Shanhua
Tainan 74199
Taiwan

+886 6 583 7801
+886 6 583 0009

info@worldveg.org
 worldveg.org